

Georgian Wheelchair Production Network

April 1, 2009 - May 31, 2014

Grant Activity Completion Report

Submitted by

World Institute on Disability (WID)

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Acknowledgements

***WID DEDICATES THIS REPORT TO
ALL THE PROJECT STAFF AND CONSULTANTS
WHOSE TIRELESS EFFORTS AND COMMITMENT
MADE THIS PROJECT POSSIBLE AND SUCCESSFUL***

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I. List of Acronyms

AR	Active Rehabilitation
CIL	Coalition for Independent Living
CCNRR	The Treatment and Educational Center of Child Neurology and Neuro Rehabilitation
DEA	Association DEA
GDC	Gori Disabled Club
GEFPOR	Georgian Foundation for Prosthetics and Orthotics
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IDP	Internally Displaced Person
IOM	International Organization of Migration
LDS	Latter Day Saints
NDC	Neuro Development Center
OSCE	Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe
OT	Occupational Therapist
PWD	Persons or person with a disability
SFSU	San Francisco State University
UEDE	Union of Employment of Disabled Entrepreneurs
UNCRPD	United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WHO	World Health Organization
WID	World Institute on Disability
WL	World Learning
WWI	Whirlwind Wheelchair International

II. Executive Summary

For 5 years, the World Institute on Disability (WID), with the assistance of Whirlwind Wheelchair International (WWI), provided international expert training and technical assistance to the Coalition for Independent Living (CIL) in order to address some of the most basic problems affecting Georgian wheelchair users: 1) Lack of affordable and maneuverable wheelchairs; 2) Lack of wheelchair mobility training; 3) High rates of unemployment of persons with disabilities; and 4) Need to remove architectural and attitudinal barriers to the full integration of persons with mobility impairments in the community.

WID established a working partnership with CIL, located in Tbilisi, the capital of Georgia, and partnerships with 2 DPOs in other regions of Georgia that are members of CIL, the Gori Disability Club and the Association DEA in Zugdidi, located in cities closest to Georgia's conflict zones and have increased numbers of disabled persons due to conflict including landmine victims and also serve IDPs with disabilities in their region. Although not the partner named in the original proposal, WID established a working partnership with the Neuro Development Center (NDC, formerly CCNDR), the only NGO providing children's rehabilitation services in Georgia and staffed with qualified occupational therapists (OT).

Georgian Wheelchair Production Network

WID's strategy and approach was to create, with our 4 Georgian NGO partners, a "**Georgian Wheelchair Production Network**," by establishing: (1) a sustainable wheelchair production and repair business in Tbilisi, which produces and sells an adult and child model of the manual RoughRider™ indoor-outdoor wheelchair; an electric version of the RoughRider™ wheelchair; pressure relief wheelchair cushions; metal folding ramps; car hand controls and other assistive mobility products for Georgian wheelchair users; (2) postural support seating products and services, according to WHO guidelines, provided by trained and certified (WHO Intermediate and Advanced Services) OTs at clinics held at NDC; (3) the local production of pressure relief cushions in Gori; and (4) small, networked wheelchair sales outreach and repair businesses in Gori and Zugdidi; and (5) supported by Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi working to improve accessibility and raise awareness of the rights and needs of persons with disabilities in their communities and provide opportunities for mobility skills training for wheelchair-users.

Wheelchair Production and Service

Much of WID's three-year initial project and 2-year supplemental funding, focused on creating and sustaining CIL wheelchair production, sales, repair and appropriate wheelchair provision according to WHO guidelines. The set-up of the wheelchair production shop and training of the workers was done by WWI. WID, WWI and CIL wanted to create a business that employed workers with disabilities, both as an employment opportunity for people who desperately need jobs and well as to demonstrate that persons with disabilities are capable of doing a variety of jobs, including metal work, in addition to producing low-cost, high-quality, locally made wheelchairs that are appropriate for active-use in the rugged Georgian urban and rural environment.

CIL has achieved the business and managerial capacity to produce and market high quality, low cost wheelchairs for adults and children using locally available and imported materials. The 5 wheelchair riders, who currently work at the wheelchair production shop and who had no previous experience in manufacturing prior to this project, have now been trained and know how to perform their jobs well enough to be able to work effectively in order to meet demanding production deadlines. Wheelchair repair mechanics have also been trained in the skills and knowledge to repair wheelchairs and have been established in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi. CIL staff has been trained on how to implement sales, marketing and public education plans and how to identify and secure international funding in order to sustain their wheelchair sales. By the end of the five-year project, CIL sold more than 3000 RoughRider™ wheelchairs to a range of buyers primarily the Georgian government through its voucher program, as well as the U.S. government, humanitarian assistance organizations and others.

New Government Tender for Purchasing Wheelchairs

In September 2013, the Government of Georgia issued a new resolution on wheelchair provision on August 22, 2013, according to which, starting from September 1, 2013, there will be a new separate state program for purchasing wheelchairs (both manual and electric) called, “*Supporting Local Wheelchair Production and Employment of PWD.*” This Government of Georgia amendment sets out eligibility criteria according to which only those local wheelchair providers are eligible to provide wheelchairs within the state program, who produce wheelchairs locally; employ PWD in their production; and have all the technical and human capacity, technology and methodology to follow the WHO guidelines on wheelchair provision, which requires basic assessment and fitting, training, technical and postural support seating service, when needed. This new resolution also requires that Georgia adhere to the international standards for wheelchair production and service outlined in the World Health Organization’s *Guidelines on the Provision of Manual Wheelchairs in less resourced settings.*

Introduction of a New Product: Electric RoughRider™

In 2013, CIL began producing electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs using a new RoughRider™ wheelchair model created in Georgia with greatly reduced armrests. This new model makes it much easier to transfer in and out of the wheelchair by quadriplegics, women with disabilities and others with limited physical strength. In addition, the relatively inexpensive electric wheelchair will afford many Georgians with significant disabilities an opportunity for independence. The Georgian government has agreed to purchase these wheelchairs for qualified individuals including a complete service package.

Postural Support Seating Service

Located in Tbilisi, NDC has its own workshop, trained occupational therapists (OT) and a sustainable history of their own domestic and international funding. International Master Seating Expert, Jamie Noon, provided NDC and OT professional staff with best practices on seating and postural support services, designing and manufacturing of postural support equipment and clinical and technical training according to WHO guidelines. Mr. Noon worked with NDC to institutionalize in their service delivery system the WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services training of OTs; the production of seating support equipment; the seating equipment vendor relationships; equipment storage and quality control inspection and the documentation of service provision and client satisfaction of adults and children through their participation in the

OT clinical training and service activities in Tbilisi and in regional cities. 34 professional OT and OT students have been trained to provide WHO Basic services, and of those 34, 12 have been trained and certified to provide WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services, including 2 internationally certified Master Trainers.

NDC now has an ongoing clinic for OTs to provide postural support services and equipment, primarily static seating, paid for by the State budget and by families who have the money to pay for the services. During the project, NDC provided 260 Basic, Intermediate and Advanced assessments and fittings as well as 93 RoughRider™ wheelchairs for low-income adults and children who needed a wheelchair replacement.

Wheelchair Mobility and Independent Living Skills Camps

WID subcontracted with a Polish international expert, Tomasz Tasiemski, PhD, who had developed a precise training course regarding the methodology of teaching wheelchair mobility and activities of daily living and produced a video manual titled, *Turning the Corner: Manual Wheelchair Skills*. Dr. Tasiemski led the first and second 5-day wheelchair mobility skills training camps for approximately 20 wheelchair users at a time in active wheelchair use, maintenance, personal care, peer counseling, parenting with a disability, and in the reproductive health issues of men and women with disabilities. CIL staff ensured adequate accessibility of the wheelchair mobility camps, held in a motel in Senaki that was made accessible for participants in wheelchairs. 5 Georgians wheelchair users (3 men and 2 women) were trained by Dr. Tasiemski in 2012 and led the third and fourth camps.

Community Public Education, Self-Empowerment and Social Advocacy Activities

3 teams of 2 Disability Advocates implemented public education and social advocacy activities in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi to increase opportunities for access to education, employment, and full participation of persons with disabilities in their communities. Momentum collectively generated by the advocacy and public education activities conducted by this project led to new DPOs being formed that focused on barrier removal as well as a second USAID-funded project focused on building the advocacy capacity of persons with disabilities and building the capacity of regional DPOs. These joint activities raised the profile of disability awareness in Georgia, even gaining the attention and support of the Prime Minister and the declaration of 2013 as the Year of Disability in Georgia.

Although the actual number of barriers removed was smaller than planned, the project targeted high profile institutions such as banks and government offices, election voting sites and the Georgian Orthodox Church, which in turn have made independent and ongoing efforts to increase accessibility at sites under their control. The project worked to increase participation of persons with disabilities in elections by providing foldable metal ramps for key voting sites (constructed by the CIL wheelchair production shop) and by using their accessible van and portable metal ramp to help transport wheelchair users to travel to their election stations on Election Day. The CIL advocacy team also consulted on making key Tbilisi tourist destinations accessible for wheelchair users including the National Cathedral; the Funicular tramway station to Mtatsminda Park (CIL has built a ramp at the lower station that allows wheelchair users to enter the tram and also installed a platform lift on the upper station); the renovation of Old Tbilisi neighborhood; the main street of Rusateveli Ave. (construction almost finished); and the

Georgian National Museum. In addition, CIL is currently working with Tbilisi City Hall to adapt the cable car station that takes people up to Narikala Castle in Old Tbilisi.

Public education and mobilization efforts also helped lead to new, significant local and national disability policies including:

- *Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for Persons with Disabilities*
- *Technical Regulations and Standards for Ensuring Architectural and Environmental Accessibility for Persons with Disabilities*
- *Ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*
- *Adoption of the law, Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination*
- *Adoption of Disabled Parking in Tbilisi*
- *Government of Georgia Resolution No. 216 on Approving the 2013 State Program on Social Rehabilitation and Childcare*

III. Management

a. Staffing, staff training, systems and procedures

American Staff

World Institute on Disability (WID) Staff

Anita Aaron, World Institute on Disability's Executive Director, supervised WID staff, monitored the submission of all required narrative and financial documents to World Learning (WL)/USAID and provided technical assistance as requested.

Bruce Curtis, WID Project Director, served as the primary contact person with all of the project partner organizations, the Coalition for Independent Living (CIL), the Neuro Development Center (NDC), Whirlwind Wheelchair International (WWI) and all international consultants; provided expert technical assistance and training; supervised the planning and implementation of all project activities and the development of project materials, publications and reports. Mr. Curtis served as the primary contact person to World Learning and USAID (Washington, DC) and was responsible for meeting all WL/USAID project reporting requirements. Mr. Curtis traveled to Georgia usually 3 times per year for approximately 2 weeks each trip during the 5 year project in order to consult with all Georgian NGO partners; conduct site visits with all partner NGOs; review status of project implementation activities; provide expert technical assistance and training; and to participate in key project activities.

Jennifer Geagan, International Program Grants Administrator, managed and monitored the project budget and expenses, consultant contracts and sub awards; regularly communicated with all American and Georgian NGO management and accounting staff regarding project financial transactions, expense documentation and financial reports. Ms. Geagan traveled to Georgia 5 times during the project to provide technical assistance, conduct site visits with Mr. Curtis of all Georgian NGO partners and to participate in key project training activities. Ms. Geagan also helped develop trainings and presentations and coordinated project evaluation activities.

American Staff Training

No specialized training in USAID regulations or procedures was provided to WID staff in order to implement their project responsibilities and activities.

Whirlwind Wheelchair International (WWI) Staff

WWI started the project as a sub award partner (under the fiscal management of San Francisco State University) with the responsibility to manage and supervise financial sub-awards for CIL in order to start up the wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop. In the 2-year Project Extension, WID continued to involve WWI as a technical consultant with no management or supervision responsibilities.

WWI provided technical assistance to WID and CIL in setting up the CIL wheelchair production business and conducting wheelchair production shop floor worker training activities. WWI staff included Marc Krizack, Executive Director, who managed and supervised Ralf Hotchkiss, Chief Engineer/Instructor; Matt McCambridge, Production Engineer; Aaron Wieler, Instructor/Quality

Control; Keoke King, Business and Marketing Trainer and WWI's Russian consultant Mr. Alexander Afonin. Mr. Krizack provided training and monitoring of CIL's administration and shop staff on wheelchair production business issues, including quality control, customer feedback, repair and maintenance of RoughRider™ wheelchairs; the set-up and operation of the two regional wheelchair sales and repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi; and monitored the CIL business management for their coordination in the national network for wheelchair sales, provision and repair.

WWI directed its consultant, Mr. Afonin, to assist in the shop equipment purchase, shop equipment and storage fabrication, equipment set up and the wheelchair production line in the first CIL wheelchair production shop in 2010, and in 2012, the relocation and setup of CIL's second wheelchair production shop with multiple workstations, quality control procedures, finished wheelchair storage, raw material storage, accessible bathrooms and an administration office.

Georgian NGO Staff

Coalition for Independent Living (CIL)

CIL Project Coordinator Giorgi Dzneladze, reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all Georgian Wheelchair Production Network (GWPN) project activities in Georgia, provided financial accounting for all project activities and submitted all required program and financial reports quarterly to WID. Mr. Dzneladze was directly responsible for supervising the creation and implementation of CIL project training activities in Georgia; organizing and implementing the Wheelchair Mobility/Independent Living Skills Camps; organizing and implementing all government advocacy initiatives and policy relationships; as well as all overseeing the production of all project publicity materials, videos, television and radio interviews, and CIL's wheelchair production and provision website and Facebook page.

Mr. Dzneladze was responsible for the management of the CIL wheelchair production business and factory shop and directly supervised Tamaz Injgia, the Wheelchair Production Shop Technical Director (Engineer), and Levan Talakhadze, Technical Director (Engineer). Both Mr. Injgia and Mr. Talakhadze jointly supervised the shop's administrative assistants and the wheelchair production team.

Mr. Dzneladze also coordinated and supervised the activities of the Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams consisting of 2 Community Accessibility Advocates, who were responsible for implementing community advocacy, public education and barrier removal activities in their communities. Mr. Dzneladze communicated regularly via e-mail and telephone with the 2 Directors of the CIL member DPOs hosting the 2 Advocacy/Community Accessibility teams in Gori and Zugdidi, made quarterly site visits to the 2 regional DPO partners, the Gori Disabled Club and the Association DEA in Zugdidi, and was responsible for sending quarterly programmatic and financial reports on the activities of the 3 Advocacy/Community Accessibility teams to WID.

The 3 DPO Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams

CIL Project Coordinator Giorgi Dzneladze, and the regional DPO Director in Gori, Tina Bregvadze, and in Zugdidi, Madonna Kharebava, each supervised their Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams. In Tbilisi, Mr. Dzneladze supervised a 2-person team, which included a Team Coordinator, Rati Ionatamishvili, and a Community Accessibility Advocate, Natalia Sadradze, who sadly passed away in 2011, succeeded by Tiko Revazashvili for the remainder of the project. The CIL wheelchair production shop in Tbilisi provided any required wheelchair repairs. In Gori, Tina Bregvadze supervised a two-person team, which included a Community Accessibility Advocate, Zviad Zviadadze, and a Wheelchair Repair Mechanic, Malkhaz Ioramashvili, who were responsible for implementing all community activities in Gori. Ms. Bregvadze also took responsibility to work as the Team Coordinator. In Zugdidi, Madonna Kharebava supervised a 3-person team, which included a Team Coordinator, Iveta Tshitashvili, a Community Accessibility Advocate, Medea Jiqia and a Wheelchair Repair Mechanic, Joni Gergedava, who were responsible for implementing all community activities in Zugdidi. All DPO Directors supervised the team coordinators and the completion of all local project activities and provided quarterly narrative and financial reports directly to the CIL Project Coordinator.

The Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi were comprised of persons with mobility disabilities, who organized and implemented community events and activities promoting disability awareness public education; independent living skills training; public demonstrations on promoting community accessibility; the improvement of community accessibility for adult and children wheelchair users through the removal of architectural and environmental barriers; information about the RoughRider™ wheelchair; wheelchair provision guidelines; Ministry of Health voucher system, wheelchair mobility skills training; and basic repair services.

Neuro Development Center (formerly The Treatment and Educational Center of Child Neurology and Neuro Rehabilitation, CCNRR) Staff

NDC Program Director, Zaza Kakushadze, was the project's manager and coordinator for the WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced classes and services provided at NDC and for a TOT course for ongoing training and certification of Occupational Therapists (OTs) and other participants. Mr. Kakushadze reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all GWPN project activities and submitted all required quarterly NDC program and financial reports to WID.

Postural support seating products and services, evaluation and manufacturing is provided at the NDC building in Tbilisi, which has its own workshop, trained OTs, and a sustainable history of their own domestic and international funding. Mr. Kakushadze managed the OTs who provided postural support seating services, training classes, equipment fitting and follow-up client satisfaction services according to WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced guidelines for adults and children who use wheelchairs.

International Expert Consultants

Jamie Noon

Master Seating Expert/Trainer Jamie Noon started in December 2009 to build adaptive seating and postural support devices for adults and children using wheelchairs. Mr. Noon, by providing expert training and a TOT course, trained NDC staff and OTs at the NDC building to understand and utilize WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced guidelines for wheelchair service provision. Mr. Noon reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all of his GWPN consulting and training activities.

Stefan Constantinescu

Stefan Constantinescu, based in Toronto Canada, is an assistive technology designer with 20 years of experience in the design and production of mobility and seating products in less resourced settings. Following his initial evaluation trip in October 2012 to evaluate the first CIL wheelchair production facility in Tbilisi at the invitation of WID and CIL, Mr. Constantinescu travelled again in September 2013 in order to evaluate the second and larger CIL wheelchair production facility. Mr. Constantinescu reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all of his GWPN consultant and training activities.

Tomasz Tasiemski, PhD.

Dr. Tomasz Tasiemski from the University School of Physical Education in Poznan, Poland was a consultant and TOT trainer for CIL in Active Rehabilitation (AR) skills for wheelchair participants during our 5-year project. Dr. Tasiemski provided a 5-day active rehabilitation and wheelchair mobility skills training camp in Senaki, Georgia for wheelchair users in 2010 and again in 2011. Dr. Tasiemski reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all of his GWPN and training activities.

Dr. Tasiemski also provided a TOT training course to 3 men and 2 women wheelchair users in 2012, who then successfully trained Georgian wheelchair users in 5-day wheelchair mobility and independent living skills training camps. The five Georgian active rehabilitation and wheelchair mobility skills trainers improved their individual practical skills and knowledge in the active rehabilitation and wheelchair mobility skills training system, and showed their ability to independently deliver all training sessions (practical and theoretical).

Salam Hassan

Mr. Hassan, an Iraqi wheelchair user, has over 20 years of experience with electrical engineering and computer programming. Mr. Hassan provided WID technical support in the development and implementation of WID, CIL and WWI fabrication efforts to create and finalize the prototype design of a RoughRider™ Electric Wheelchair. Mr. Hassan reported to the WID project director on the implementation of all of his RoughRider™ Electric Wheelchair consultant activities.

Independent Evaluator

As part of the completion of the project, WID contracted with an independent evaluator to conduct a final project evaluation in order to establish lessons learned and to identify the achievements of the Original (2009-2012) and Extension Projects (2012-2014). The Independent

Evaluator, Marc Behrendt, Behrendt Consulting, London, United Kingdom, designed and conducted a final performance evaluation, including collecting data, analyzing the data, compiling findings and recommendations and producing a report per USAID requirements. The Independent Evaluator traveled to Georgia for 20 days to implement project evaluation activities.

Systems and Procedures

As the GWPN Project Lead Agency, WID managed the project from its offices in Oakland and then Berkeley, California and coordinated and supervised WWI, CIL and NDC/CCNNR and the international consultants in the coordination and implementation of all project activities. WID sent quarterly program and financial reports to WL/USAID and was responsible for meeting WL grant management requirements.

WID staff made technical assistance and training site visits each year to the Georgian NGO partners. WID, WWI and their international consultants led all Georgian-based trainings. WID trained all partners on providing quarterly plans and reports and provided feedback, including making inquiries about what was planned and what actually happened, what additional activities were carried out, why were certain activities canceled or postponed. WID evaluated and provided feedback to CIL, WWI and NDC on their project reports and plans; consulted every two weeks at a minimum with all project partners in order to successfully carry out project activities; reviewed and modified, if necessary, all training curricula, guides, and brochures; and participated in the final project evaluation.

All 3 of the Disability Advocacy and Community Accessibility teams received bi-annual visits by WID staff. WID and CIL provided knowledge, skills and practice based training to members of the Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi Disability Advocacy and Community Accessibility teams on how to effectively implement community advocacy, public education events and barrier removal activities and how to write accurate quarterly reports.

b. Coordination

WID staff maintained project communications and coordination with our WWI partner, international consultants and Georgian NGO partners through daily e-mails and Skype conference meetings every few weeks. WID, with all of our partners' input, successfully developed and received WL/USAID approval for all budgets, work plans and strategies for strengthening the amount and quality of services delivered throughout the GWPN project. In order to more effectively coordinate all project activities, during all site visits to Georgia, WID conducted extensive face-to-face meetings with all project partners, international consultants, and, when appropriate, U.S. and Georgian government authorities and other international and Georgian NGOs who were collaborating with CIL or should be collaborating with CIL.

In order to support effective management and coordination of daily project activities by all partnering NGOs in Georgia, WID provided a sub award to CIL to provide staff, offices, operational support and coordination for the GWPN from their offices in Tbilisi, and CIL provided small subgrants to their 2 member DPOs in Gori and Zugdidi to implement and coordinate all project activities in their regions. Mr. Dzneladze coordinated project activities by communicating regularly via e-mail, telephone and personal meetings with the CIL wheelchair

production shop, NDC and with the Directors of the 3 Advocacy/Community Accessibility teams. Mr. Dzeladze also coordinated project activities by conducting daily or weekly visits to the wheelchair production shop; making quarterly site visits to the 2 regional DPO partners; and was responsible for sending quarterly programmatic and financial reporting on the activities of the CIL wheelchair production shop and the 3 Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility teams to WID.

In order to support effective management and coordination of CIL's daily wheelchair production business and shop activities by WWI, WID also provided a sub award to WWI (in project Years 1-3) to manage, coordinate and supervise all training activities related to setting up and implementing the CIL wheelchair production business and the wheelchair production shop. WWI's Director, Mr. Krizack, maintained weekly communications and coordination with his international consultant, Mr. Afonin, and with CIL through daily e-mails and Skype conference meetings every few weeks or as needed.

In order to support effective management and coordination of daily project activities by NDC, WID also provided a sub award to NDC to manage, coordinate and supervise all project activities related to setting up and implementing postural support seating services, equipment and seating cushion fabrication and training courses according to WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced guidelines. Mr. Kakushadze coordinated project activities by communicating with WID, international consultants and the OTs through weekly meetings, e-mails or Skype calls. Mr. Kakushadze coordinated project activities by communicating with CIL or Mr. Noon through personal meetings, telephone conversations and e-mails every few weeks or more often if needed. Mr. Kakushadze participated in Skype conference meetings with WID and/or Mr. Noon every few weeks or more often when required in order to coordinate project activities or to solve technical problems. Mr. Kakushadze also maintained close communication and coordination with Mr. Noon in order to manage and provide logistical support for all trainings provided by Mr. Noon while he was in Georgia.

c. Supervision and Monitoring, Technical Assistance

Project Activities

WID supervised and monitored the progress of planned project activities of WWI, international consultants, and all Georgian NGO partners through Skype conversations, e-mails and quarterly reports. WID supervised and monitored all country visits to NGO partners for training or consultation by WWI and the international consultants; by pre-visit planning conversations through Skype or e-mails and by debriefing conversations after returning from their trips; and through their trip reports.

The WID project director traveled to Georgia usually 3 times per year for approximately 2 weeks each trip during the 5 year project, in order to provide supervision and monitoring of the status of all project activities; consult face-to-face with all Georgian NGO partners, while reviewing their previous and future planned activities; conduct site visits with all partner NGOs in order to personally observe project successes, lack of successes and to witness the day-to-day reality encountered by our project partners; provide personal technical assistance and training whenever needed; and to participate in important project implementation or training activities.

The WID project director and grants administrator, and, if necessary, WWI, international consultants or CIL were available to provide technical assistance whenever any project partner or team member requested expert opinions or professional assistance in resolving obstacles encountered while trying to implement project activities. For example, the WID grants administrator provided explanations and technical assistance to the CIL accountant, Inga Mamaladze, in order to improve her understanding of WL/USAID financial report requirements and WID financial management reporting guidelines and procedures. The WID project director also provided technical assistance to the CIL project interpreter/administrator, Tamuna Nadiradze, on how to correctly fill out the quarterly indicators form.

Financial Management

WID managed all project funds through its grants administrator who, with the assistance of the project director, worked closely with the WID Director of Finance. The WID Director of Finance maintained records for project funds in a separate cost center, applied all generally accepted accounting principles in its financial procedures, and reviewed and approved all quarterly financial reports to WL/USAID using project funds. As usual, WID conducted an independent audit and an A-133 federal audit of its financial activities each fiscal year.

The WID grants administrator provided technical assistance to all American and Georgian NGO partners, consultants and regional teams on financial reporting requirements and on WL/USAID procedures for appropriately managing project funds. WID's grants administrator monitored the correct submission of all WWI/SFSU quarterly project financial reports and provided technical assistance as required.

WID's grants administrator monitored the submission of all CIL project financial reports, including the 2 regional DPO advocacy and community accessibility teams, the wheelchair production business, and the proper use and accounting of all project funds. CIL communicated regularly with WID staff by Skype calls and e-mails in order to ensure the effective management of all project funding; discuss any necessary changes in budget line items; and to answer any financial questions submitted by WID as required by WL/USAID.

d. Office, Sub-offices and Logistic support

WID, as the lead project agency, utilized its offices in Oakland and then Berkeley, CA to manage and coordinate all programmatic and financial activities of the project. WID supervised and coordinated all international consultant activities and provided logistical support as required to all project partners and consultants.

WWI utilized its offices in San Francisco, CA to manage and coordinate all programmatic, financial and logistical support activities related to providing training and technical assistance to WID and CIL on setting up a wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop in Tbilisi, Georgia.

CIL as the lead country-coordinating agency utilized its offices in Tbilisi, Georgia to implement, manage and coordinate all programmatic and financial activities of the project in Georgia. CIL

coordinated, supervised and provided logistical support in Georgia as required by any project partner or international consultant.

The Gori Disability Club, located in the city of Gori, and the Association DEA, located in the city of Zugdidi, utilized their DPO offices to provide management, implementation, coordination and logistical support for all programmatic and financial activities related to the project in these two regions.

The Neuro Development Center, located in Tbilisi, Georgia, utilized its offices to provide programmatic and financial management and to coordinate the implementation and logistical support for all project activities related to professional training and the fabrication and provision of postural support equipment and services according to WHO guidelines.

IV. Program Accomplishments by Results

a. Program implementation approach and methodology

Georgian Environment

When the project began in 2009, one year after the war with Russia and six years after the Rose Revolution, the Georgian government and people were transitioning from being a post-Soviet country with centralized legal, economic and social planning, with Georgian families (especially adults and children who use wheelchairs) still struggling with the legacy of inaccessible public and housing infrastructure; bad neighborhood roads; negative public attitudes and stereotypes about children and adults using wheelchairs; social invisibility of persons using wheelchairs; wheelchairs occasionally provided for free by international humanitarian donors with minimal or no wheelchair provision; and with no public or professional understanding about international standards for appropriate wheelchair provision through assessment, fitting and mobility skills training.

Georgian families and professionals are usually unfamiliar and clueless about wheelchair differences and typically ask, “What is the cheapest wheelchair?” Before WID’s GWPN project started in 2009, the benefits and technology of WHO Intermediate Support Seating products and services for adults and children in wheelchairs was also unknown and unavailable in Georgia. Georgian families and medical professionals were completely unaware of WHO Intermediate products and services, their social inclusion benefits and long-term health advantages for the wheelchair user.

Project Implementation Strategy and Approach

For 5 years, from July 1, 2009 until May 31, 2014, WID provided international expert training and technical assistance to CIL in order to address four of the most basic problems affecting Georgian wheelchair users: 1) Lack of affordable and maneuverable wheelchairs; 2) Lack of wheelchair mobility training; 3) High rates of PWD unemployment; and 4) Need to remove architectural and attitudinal barriers to the full integration of persons with mobility impairments in the community.

WID established a working partnership with CIL, located in Tbilisi, the capital of Georgia, founded in 2002 and made up of over 25 DPOs and NGOs representing all disabilities and most geographical regions of Georgia. Disabled women hold leadership positions in CIL and manage the department focused on addressing disabled women's issues. WID also established working partnerships with 2 DPOs in other regions of Georgia that are members of CIL, the Gori Disability Club and the Association DEA in Zugdidi. Both DPOs are led by disabled women, are located in cities closest to Georgia’s conflict zones and have increased numbers of disabled persons due to conflict including landmine victims, and also serve IDPs with disabilities in their region. Although not the partner named in the original proposal, WID established a working partnership with the Neuro Development Center (NDC, formerly CCNNR), the only NGO providing children’s rehabilitation services in Georgia and staffed with qualified occupational therapists (OT). NDC and the OTs agreed to collaborate with WID and CIL on this Project.

Georgian Wheelchair Production Network

WID's strategy and approach was to create, with our 4 Georgian NGO partners, a "**Georgian Wheelchair Production Network**," by establishing: (1) a sustainable wheelchair production and repair business in Tbilisi, which produces and sells an adult and child model of the manual RoughRider™ indoor-outdoor wheelchair; an electric version of the RoughRider™ wheelchair; pressure relief wheelchair cushions; metal folding ramps; car hand controls and other assistive mobility products for Georgian wheelchair users; (2) postural support seating products and services, according to WHO guidelines, provided by trained and certified (WHO Intermediate and Advanced Services) OTs at clinics held at NDC; (3) the local production of pressure relief cushions in Gori; and (4) small, networked wheelchair sales outreach and repair businesses in Gori and Zugdidi; and (5) supported by Disability Advocacy/Community Accessibility Teams in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi working to improve accessibility and raise awareness of the rights and needs of persons with disabilities in their communities and provide opportunities for mobility skills training for wheelchair-users.

Wheelchair Production and Service

Much of WID's three-year initial project and 2-year supplemental funding, focused on creating and sustaining CIL wheelchair production, sales, repair and appropriate wheelchair provision according to WHO guidelines. The set-up of the wheelchair production shop and training of the workers was done by WWI, a longtime partner of WID and also located in the San Francisco Bay Area with more than 25 years of experience setting up small wheelchair production shops in several countries. WID, WWI and CIL wanted to create a business that employed workers with disabilities, both as an employment opportunity for people who desperately need jobs and well as to demonstrate that persons with disabilities are capable of doing a variety of jobs, including metal work, in addition to producing low-cost, high-quality, locally made wheelchairs that are appropriate for active-use in the rugged Georgian urban and rural environment.

Government Funding for Wheelchair Sales

Government funding for purchasing and subsidizing wheelchairs is via a competitive national tender offer and wheelchair provision is managed under the Ministry of Health national voucher system. In 2010, the Ministry of Health introduced a national voucher system for subsidizing wheelchair purchases for low-income persons, and every year since, CIL has successfully implemented the Ministry of Health's administrative process for utilizing vouchers to complete the sale and provision of RoughRider™ wheelchairs. CIL's business plan requires each year that CIL must compete and win this government tender and successfully administer their voucher program of which are provision in order to ensure the financial sustainability of the CIL wheelchair production business. However, government tenders for wheelchair purchases require CIL to provide a variety of wheelchair types to meet individual needs.

International Donors for Wheelchair Sales

In 2011, CIL was effective in convincing government authorities to increase the number of wheelchair vouchers as well as to construct a government tender and selection process, which favored Georgian businesses producing wheelchairs (CIL is the only Georgian business making wheelchairs). CIL also educated the government authorities about the importance of requiring wheelchair provision, by any successful vendor, according to WHO guidelines (assessment, fitting and training). Due to these educational efforts, by 2014, CIL had no other competitors for

the government wheelchair tender and serviced all available wheelchair voucher customers. Further increasing the government budget for meeting the current and future need of adults and children wheelchair users for an appropriate wheelchair will take additional time. Therefore, CIL is trying to increase sales from large institutional customers as well as from individuals through public advertising and wheelchair quality guarantees, support services and buy back offers.

At this time, humanitarian and international NGO donations of wheelchairs in Georgia are purchased from CIL and from China. Until mid 2014, the combined yearly number of CIL wheelchair sales was not quite sufficient to sustain the economic viability of the wheelchair production business. The CIL wheelchair production business needs to continue to lower its costs and grow its list of buyers, production volume and wheelchair model diversity to become economically sustainable under Georgian market constraints.

Postural Support Seating Service

After the project was funded and after lengthy discussions with WID, CIL and Jamie Noon, it was agreed that the best implementing partner for the postural support seating component of the project, including products and services, evaluation and manufacturing, and the best place to embed this service for sustainability after the project ends was NDC (originally CCNNR at the beginning of the project; their name changed in 2012). Located in Tbilisi, NDC has its own workshop, trained Occupational Therapists (OT), and a sustainable history of their own domestic and international funding. International Master Seating Expert, Jamie Noon, provided NDC and OT professional staff with best practices on seating and postural support services, designing and manufacturing of postural support equipment and clinical and technical training according to WHO guidelines. Mr. Noon worked with NDC to institutionalize in their service delivery system the WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services training of OTs; the production of seating support equipment; the seating equipment vendor relationships; equipment storage and quality control inspection and the documentation of service provision and client satisfaction of adults and children through their participation in the OT clinical training and service activities in Tbilisi and in regional cities.

Pressure Relieving Wheelchair Cushions

Medical professionals and Georgian spinal cord injured wheelchair users often do not understand the urgent need for pressure relief cushions and do not know that Georgian produced pressure relief cushions became available for purchase from CIL in June 2010. During the first year of the project, Jamie Noon provided training to the CIL, NDC and GDC staff on how to design a low-cost, high quality cushion from locally available materials based on previously successful designs. Jamie Noon also provided ongoing training and supervision in the design and manufacturing of high quality, pressure-relieving wheelchair cushions to GDC, which has the best capacity to deliver a quality product at the lowest cost, in order to generate sufficient income to sustain the cushion fabrication business.

Community Public Education, Self-Empowerment and Social Advocacy Activities

WID proposed to implement needed public education and social advocacy activities that would empower wheelchair users and encourage their families and other members of the communities in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi to increase opportunities for access to education, employment, and full participation of persons with disabilities in their communities. Over the 5 years of the

project, WID and CIL provided training seminars, skills and knowledge training, and technical assistance for 3 teams of 2 Disability Advocates. CIL, located in Tbilisi, coordinated and supported the activities of the Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi teams. All of the advocacy team members were invited and most of them participated in all international training seminars provided by WID and CIL.

Community Accessibility Issues for Persons with Mobility Impairments

In Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi, wheelchair users have traditionally been excluded from the social and political life of their communities and have been isolated from the community. These disabled people are marginalized and deprived of the opportunities available to non-disabled citizens. For the majority of PWD, participating in society is a series of often insurmountable obstacles, which they face daily both at home and in the community because of physical and attitudinal barriers and other forms of discrimination. Accessible transportation is either not available or not affordable, and many disabled youth with mobility impairments often find it almost impossible to leave their homes. Many wheelchair users and their families live in inaccessible apartments and get little or no assistance from government agencies to improve this situation. Assistive devices, such as wheelchairs, are often not available, inappropriate or are considered too costly. Youth with mobility impairments face additional physical and attitudinal barriers to their education and employment. With their social and physical isolation, wheelchair users in Georgia are poorly integrated within the larger disability community and rarely meet with older PWDs who could serve as role models or personal mentors. From all of these factors, wheelchair users experience isolation and low self-esteem and they face-overwhelming barriers to participation in the social and economic life of their communities.

WID and CIL have both understood that in order to be successful at introducing and sustaining wheelchair provision services according to WHO guidelines in Georgia, it would be necessary to simultaneously and synergistically address the social, attitudinal and access problems currently facing adult and child wheelchair users in Georgia. Therefore, WID and CIL prioritized efforts to remove access barriers at important religious, historical and environmental sites as an essential foundation for building accessible communities and for increasing social and recreational access for adults and children who use wheelchairs. In order to substantially address the current Georgian reality of a lack of accessibility and social inclusion, WID and CIL developed activities, implemented by our advocacy teams of wheelchair users in three cities, which directly increased the effectiveness of local wheelchair provision services; wheelchair mobility and independent living skills classes; and local wheelchair repair services, while improving opportunities for community and cultural integration, positive public attitudes, and an increasingly accessible public infrastructure and environment.

WID also believed that by providing small amounts of project funding to the community advocacy teams to facilitate the removal of local access barriers (an offer of financial assistance could attract and leverage building owners to provide completion construction funding for access ramps to their buildings), the community advocacy teams could remove some wheelchair access barriers at important cultural, religious and natural sites. This has proven to be a slow but realistic strategy for building more accessible communities and for increasing social and cultural access opportunities for wheelchair users.

b. Project activities

Original Proposal Objective 1: To establish a national network for the production, repair and distribution of wheelchairs and other mobility assistance and adaptive equipment.

CIL Wheelchair Production Shop Set-Up and Worker Training

After finalizing contracts and protocols, in the 3rd Quarter, the building to be used for the wheelchair production shop was renovated, including constructing an accessible bathroom for the workers who use wheelchairs. Necessary equipment and materials was purchased and accessible workstations were set-up. WWI staff and consultants helped set up the shop and train the workers in November-December 2009.

Starting in 2010, WWI staff relied on its Russian consultant, Mr. Afonin, to work 6 months out of the year in Georgia to help set up the wheelchair production shop and train the Georgian production team. This time intensive use of the Russian consultant on the ground in Georgia worked amazingly well and beyond everyone's expectations. Fully equipping the first CIL production shop with machine tools, cabinets and workspaces also included the creative construction of some equipment in order to reduce costs. All materials for the ongoing production of the wheelchairs were purchased and placed in storage on-site. Mr. Afonin also finished the creation and installation of a hand-made powder-coat paint system, including spray booth and a double oven, at a cost estimated to be 1/3 that of purchasing new equipment. The oven has dual controls that allow half the oven to be used at one time, thus saving on energy costs when small amounts of parts are painted. The spray booth has a color powder recovery system that is "environmentally green," allowing them to completely re-use the excess powders, thus being economical as well as satisfying the SIEE negative determination.

The Gori Disabled Club's sewing business for deaf women and the Union of Employment of Disabled Entrepreneurs (UEDE), another CIL member DPO, were identified to produce fabric components, comfort and pressure relieving cushions for the wheelchairs produced.

In March 2010, wheelchair production workers and mechanics were trained in Basic assessment by Jamie Noon, and by June 2010, all necessary machines and tools had been purchased and installed at the first CIL production shop, and several RoughRider™ wheelchairs were completed and given to individuals for field-testing and for reporting on their quality and effectiveness in the Georgian environment. The shop workers were also considered sufficiently trained and experienced.

Wheelchair Production, Quality Control and USAID Branding

In May 2011, WWI's Mr. Afonin and Mr. Wieler provided training to the Georgian factory workers in Whirlwind's quality control process. WWI staff provided the CIL production shop with extensive Quality Control checklists and with specified procedures to be followed to ensure good quality production of wheelchairs. Quality control inspection of the first CIL production shop techniques became a standard and ongoing procedure and a finished wheelchair prototype was shipped to WWI for quality inspection and certification. After receiving a positive WWI certification, the CIL wheelchair production shop started producing larger numbers of RoughRider™ wheelchairs. All wheelchairs have USAID and CIL logos on the X-brace tubes. All project educational materials for public distribution produced by CIL and all postural support intermediate products and project materials for public distribution produced by NDC are distributed with a USAID logo sticker before they are distributed to the client.

Wheelchair Sales and Provision

During the 6th Quarter, the first 100 wheelchairs purchased by the Georgian government were provided to clients by CIL, and during the 7th Quarter, the LDS Church purchased their first 100 RoughRider™ wheelchairs and conducted wheelchair provision via their own network. By the end of the 3rd year of the project, approximately 750 wheelchairs had been produced and sold to the Georgian government and other local and international donors.

National Voucher System

In 2010, the Ministry of Health issued vouchers for wheelchairs to some of the people on their national waiting list, and the vouchers subsidized 95% or 100% of the wheelchair cost depending on the level of poverty of the voucher-holders (i.e. if the person was below poverty line, he/she received a 100% voucher and if not, then a 95% voucher). These wheelchair users came to CIL with their vouchers and CIL staff had to fill in the wheelchair assessment and fitting form and provide wheelchairs according to their individual specifications. In 2010, when the state issued letters to voucher-holders, they gave them a deadline to pick up their vouchers. However, CIL did not have a specific deadline to complete these transactions, and therefore, after all of the wheelchairs were delivered, CIL was paid at the end of the fiscal year. In 2011, the government voucher system stated that it supported a free market choice for all persons who needed a

wheelchair. The voucher holder, influenced by their personal knowledge and experience, friends and family member's opinions, was responsible for deciding:

- What business/wheelchair provider had wheelchairs to purchase?
- What type of wheelchair to buy with their voucher?

However, the reality in Georgia is that many persons with disabilities and their families are usually unfamiliar and clueless about international wheelchair differences and typically ask, "What is the cheapest wheelchair?" Common knowledge and practice about purchasing wheelchairs was to buy a wheelchair from the medical products store in the nearest city or, if necessary, in the big commercial cities of Batumi or Tbilisi. Medical products stores in Georgia import their wheelchairs from Turkey or China and typically offer only inexpensive models. In order to increase wheelchair sales and to capture the largest market share of these voucher holders, CIL developed a public marketing plan and a system of telephone sales calls to the eligible list of holders of vouchers in order to educate them about the positive benefits of selecting the CIL RoughRider™ wheelchair and follow-up support service. No other wheelchair importer and reseller could offer the same wheelchair quality guarantees or follow-up support services as CIL.

In 2011, voucher-holders were required to collect their vouchers by a specific date, and CIL was required to deliver wheelchairs sometime during the fiscal year of 2011, but there were complications regarding the vouchers. A voucher for a partially subsidized wheelchair was 300 GEL (approximately \$180) only. The Ministry promised to subsidize the first 100 vouchers, which means they paid the remaining 150 GEL to the voucher-holder to get the wheelchair from CIL. For the 100% subsidized vouchers (300 GEL), they issued them to voucher-holders in a free-spending manner. Each voucher-holder was free to decide whether to buy a cheap Chinese/Turkish wheelchair from a local medical product store or to pay out of his/her own pockets to get a RoughRider™ from CIL. This new "anti-monopoly policy" voucher regulation put CIL in an unfair and noncompetitive position, while in direct competition with other Georgian importing companies who can import cheap wheelchairs and still receive some profit from the government voucher price of 300 GEL. CIL could not sell RoughRider™ at that price, and only a few people, if any at all, would agree to pay extra money out of their own pockets to buy RoughRider™ wheelchairs.

CIL was (and is) the only wheelchair production business in the Caucasus region since there are none in Armenia and Azerbaijan. Instead of killing off the only existing wheelchair factory, under the government's argument of a so-called "anti-monopoly policy," CIL argued that the government should support the existing Georgian wheelchair production business and create a favorable environment for Georgian wheelchair production competition to develop, but, at that time, CIL was unable to persuade the government authorities with this argument, so they instead collaborated with the government authorities to create a document on voucher distribution, which would be more or less acceptable for competing wheelchair provider businesses.

CIL's business plan requires each year that CIL must compete and win the government tender for purchasing wheelchairs and successfully administer the State voucher program in order to ensure the financial sustainability of the CIL wheelchair production business. The government tender for wheelchair purchases requires CIL to provide a variety of wheelchair types to meet

individual needs. Besides the adult and children RoughRiders™ and power wheelchairs, the CIL workshop can also provide standard Chinese wheelchairs, which can be adjusted in size and somewhat customized. As for sports wheelchairs, CIL can provide them only if there is a confirmed and worthwhile order.

Government Budget for Disability

The government budget for disability in 2011 was 6,671,100 GEL of which 196,000 GEL was for wheelchairs and 656,700 GEL for children's habilitation/rehabilitation program (NDC falls under this category). In 2011, CIL was effective in convincing government authorities to begin increasing the number of wheelchair vouchers as well as to construct a government tender and selection process, which favored Georgian businesses producing wheelchairs. CIL also educated the government authorities about the importance of requiring wheelchair provision according to WHO guidelines (assessment, fitting and training).

Pressure Relieving Wheelchair Cushions

Medical professionals and Georgian spinal cord injured wheelchair users often do not understand the urgent need for pressure relief cushions and are unaware that Georgian produced pressure relief cushions became available for purchase from CIL in June 2010. During the first year of the project, Jamie Noon provided training to the CIL, NDC and GDC staff on how to design a low-cost, high quality cushion from locally available materials based on previously successful designs. Jamie Noon also provided ongoing training and supervision in the design and manufacturing of high quality, pressure-relieving wheelchair cushions to GDC, which has the best capacity to deliver a quality product at the lowest cost, in order to generate sufficient income to sustain the cushion fabrication business.

Wheelchair User Manuals and Promotional Materials

The CIL team translated the three RoughRider™ user manuals (*Your RoughRider™ Wheelchair; Wheelchair Riding Skills; Repair & Maintenance*) into Georgian, and a large number of these 3 manuals were printed and distributed to new owners when they received their RoughRiders™. CIL produced a PSA video (25 seconds) to promote the RoughRider™ wheelchair and produced a RoughRider™ wheelchair promotional video to educate the public. CIL also purchased a website domain, www.etli.ge (in English, <http://etli.ge/index.php?lang=en>) and designed a website featuring CIL's ongoing wheelchair production and the other products and services offered by CIL. The website was launched in Georgian, English and Russian languages.

Joni Gergedava, Zugdidi, and Malkhaz Ioramashvili, Gori, being trained in wheelchair repair

Regional Wheelchair Repair Shops

The project intended to set up wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi during the first 3 years of the project, but their establishment was ultimately delayed until the beginning of the 4th year. In December 2011, CIL wheelchair production specialists Levan Talakhadze and Tamaz Injgia, with help from WWI consultant Mr. Afonin, conducted a week-long training in wheelchair maintenance and repair for Joni Gergedava from Zugdidi and Malkhaz Ioramashvili from Gori, who were trained to be mechanics at the wheelchair repair shops to be created in Gori and Zugdidi. Both mechanics were also trained in Basic assessment and participated in other project advocacy activities until the shops were set-up in the 13th Quarter.

Original Proposal Objective 2: To establish a mobility, self-care, independent living and community accessibility advocacy skill training system for men and women who use wheelchairs in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills Camps

WID subcontracted with a Polish international expert, Tomasz Tasiemski, PhD, who had developed a precise training course regarding the methodology of teaching wheelchair mobility and activities of daily living and produced a video manual titled, *Turning the Corner: Manual Wheelchair Skills*. His training materials were translated into Georgian and made available to the Georgian wheelchair mobility skill trainers. WID's Project Director, the CIL Project coordinator and Dr. Tasiemski are all wheelchair users, and they all participated in specialized training camps on active wheelchair use, maintenance and in activities of daily living.

In Quarter 6 and Quarter 10, WID, CIL and Dr. Tasiemski conducted 5-day wheelchair mobility skills training camp (20 wheelchair users 10 men and 10 women in September 2010 in Q6, and 19 wheelchair users 14 men and 5 women in September 2011, in Q10) in active wheelchair use, maintenance, personal care, peer counseling, parenting with a disability, and in the reproductive health issues of men and women with disabilities. CIL staff conducted preparatory activities to

Dr. Tasiemski (brown cap) with some of the camp participants going to the Sports Gym.

guarantee adequate accessibility of the Senaki wheelchair mobility and independent living skills training camps, in a new motel that was made accessible for participants in wheelchairs.

A wheelchair mobility course was constructed and utilized along with other training accessories including cones, balls and other items for wheelchair games. In addition to the wheelchair-user

Tina Bregvadze, Gori Disabled Club Director learning wheelchair mobility skills

camp participants, 2 Georgian trainers, who are wheelchair-users, assisted Dr. Tasiemski. Also supporting the camp participants were 5 able-bodied assistants, one wheelchair mechanic, one occupational therapist, one nurse and two interpreters also supported the camp activities.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills One-Day Events

During the 2nd year of the project, WID and CIL agreed that the cost and logistical complexity, in addition to the availability of potential participants, was making it impossible to achieve the target number of camps and persons receiving mobility skills training. Therefore, WID, CIL and the 3 Advocacy Teams developed and implemented one-day mobility skills events where basic wheelchair use and repair skills were demonstrated and practiced as well as information about independent living and personal care skills for wheelchair-users presented. 10 one-day mobility skills events were held during the 3rd project year, including an event conducted by the CIL team at an institution in Dusheti.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills One-Day Events in Gori (top) and Zugdidi (bottom)

Postural Support Seating Services for Children and Adults in Wheelchairs

International expert, Jamie Noon, provided NDC (CCNNR at that time) and OT professional staff with best practices on seating and postural support services, designing and manufacturing postural support equipment, and clinical and technical training according to WHO guidelines. Mr. Noon helped to institutionalize the WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services training system; the OT training system; the design and production of a pressure relieving cushion; the production of seating support equipment; the seating equipment vendor relationships; equipment storage and quality control inspection and the documentation of service provision and client satisfaction of adults and children through their participation in the OT clinical training and service activities in Tbilisi and in regional cities.

Postural support seating products and services, evaluation and manufacturing is provided at NDC in Tbilisi, which has its own workshop, trained Occupational Therapists (OT), and a sustainable history of their own domestic and international funding. International expert seating and postural support, clinical and technical training according to WHO guidelines, was provided to NDC and OT professional staff by Jamie Noon. CIL, NDC and OT professional staff were trained together, according to WHO Basic guidelines, on the correct procedures for measuring wheelchair users for a wheelchair and a cushion.

WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced Training Classes

The first Basic training was conducted by Jamie Noon in March 2010 with wheelchair shop workers. A Basic and Intermediate training was conducted in June 2010 followed by an Advanced training in February 2011 for 5 OTs.

The first Basic Wheelchair Provision training was conducted by Jamie Noon

Basic Wheelchair Provision Practical Course Outline:

Day 1: Introduction; Wheelchair users; Anatomy; and Pressure sores. 2: Cushions; Wheelchairs; Wheelchair skills; and Wheelchair provision. 3: Practical assessments (Two groups of users); 4: Practical equipment preparation; Practical fitting; and Practical user training. 5: Case presentations; Review key points; Written test; and Closing.

Intermediate Wheelchair Provision Practical Course Outline:

Day 1: Introduction; Wheelchair users; and Anatomy review Benefits. 2: Postures; Postural support devices; and Supporting postures. 3: Posture game; Supporting postures; Modifications; and Available products. 4: Posture game; Conditions and considerations; Imaginary friends; and Assessment. 5: Posture game; Fitting and follow up; User training; Service; and Written test. 6: Practical assessments and Equipment set up. 7: Practical assessments and Equipment set up. 8: Practical equipment set up and Individual test and feedback. 9: Practical fittings. 10: Case presentations; Review key points; Plan for independent work and Advanced course.

Independent Practice Cases

After completing the 5-day Basic course and the 10-day Intermediate course, each training participant spent 2 to 6 months in their usual workplace and completed a minimum of 3 client cases of independent practice for each course level. Full documentation of the practice client cases was sent to the course trainer for review and feedback and any follow up documentation was also sent to the trainer for review. The course trainer selected one client case from each participant, and the participant prepared a presentation on that case and presented during the Advanced course.

The course trainer maintained organized records of all monitoring, feedback and grading of participants throughout the course and their “Provisional Practitioner” period.

WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced TOT

In September 2011, NDC helped organized the training room and support logistics for Jamie Noon to provide an expert Training Of Trainers WHO Basic and Intermediate and advanced course at the NDC building for the ongoing skills and knowledge training of OT participants.

Some of the OTs, who were preparing to be teachers in the first TOT, provided assistance in translating the Basic and Intermediate training sessions into the Georgian language.

A 5 day TOT was conducted by Jamie Noon and attended by:

- Nino Rukhadze (Certified in Basic and Intermediate)
- Ilo Valshakov (Certified in Basic and Intermediate)
- Rusiko Lortkianidze (Certified in Basic and Intermediate)
- Levan Talakhadze (Certified in Basic)

Theory on Wheelchair Provision TOT Outline:

Day 1: Introduction; Case presentations and feedback; Share training experiences; Intro to interactive methodology; Intro to Participant pack; Course logistics; and User selection and support. 2: Pairs prepare sessions. 3: Pairs run sessions/feedback. 4: Pairs run sessions/feedback. 5: How to grade participants; Record keeping; Trainer responsibilities and professional ethics; Professional progression overview; Theory exam; Master Trainer feedback to new Trainers; and Review and final instruction.

The Basic and Intermediate Wheelchair Provision Practical Course Taught by OTs

After the 5 days of Theory and as part of the TOT requirements, three of the new Trainers (Rusiko Lortkianidze, Nino Rukhadze and Ilo Valshakov) delivered the Basic and Intermediate courses with 7 participants in each course. In September 2011, the first 5-day Basic course was taught by the 3 new Georgian OT trainers with direct support from Jamie Noon. In October 2011, the first 10-day Intermediate course was conducted by the 3 new Georgian OT trainers, also with direct support from Jamie Noon.

Wheelchair Provision and Screening Training Workshops with Social Workers

CIL training for 18 social workers at the Ministry of Health

In February 2012, CIL began conducting periodic 1-day workshops for social workers working for the Ministry of Labor, Healthcare and Social Affairs as social agents in communities

throughout Georgia. This training for social workers provided basic disability awareness and information about the quality and mobility differences between various models of wheelchairs including the RoughRider™ wheelchair. CIL planned to utilize the community networks of the social workers in order to educate their clients who need wheelchairs about the different choices available when using their vouchers. Appropriately trained social workers could help to reduce the time required by CIL to answer basic questions from wheelchair voucher recipients.

Original Proposal Objective 3: To establish business and advocacy networks between disability communities in Georgia by implementing advocacy, public education, and community accessibility barrier removal activities for persons with mobility impairments and wheelchair users in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi.

Community Accessibility, Public Education And Advocacy Team Seminars

During the 3rd and 4th quarters, Disability Advocacy Team members received group advocacy training to help them effectively implement project activities. Team members learned to: 1) Educate and mobilize other mobility impaired youth and wheelchair users in the community to promote a Barrier Free Community environment through disability awareness training and public presentations; 2) Identify and recruit professional allies (teachers, lawyers, journalists, government authorities) into a cross sector community coalition; 3) Raise public awareness in the schools and community about issues related to a Barrier Free Community for children and young adults with mobility impairments; 4) Remove physical barriers at strategic community facilities; 5) Use disability awareness videos to educate the public about the need for a Barrier Free Community environment; and 6) Sustain these efforts using local community resources. WID and CIL were responsible for directly organizing and implementing all training and project activities with the Disability Advocacy teams.

In the 10th Quarter, CIL (5) staff, including the CIL Advocacy Team, participated in a 5-day study tour to Poland on “Polish Experience in Socio – Vocational Rehabilitation and Integration of People with Disabilities,” sponsored and paid for by the Polish Secretary of State at the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy.

Community Accessibility, Public Education And Advocacy Team Activities

Identification, Outreach and Mobilization and the Mobilization of Wheelchair Users and Persons with Mobility Impairments: During each project year, the Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi teams conducted outreach to identify men and women wheelchair users and persons with mobility impairments and to recruit them as volunteers. The teams led roundtable peer support groups, disability awareness, and community access and barrier-removal trainings for wheelchair users and persons with mobility impairments in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi and tried to reach and involve wheelchair users in rural communities in their regions. In addition, the Gori and Zugdidi teams, who live in the cities closest to the conflict zones of South Ossetia and Abkhazia respectively, Gori being on the front line of the most recent 2008 war with Russia, regularly reached out to Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in their locales to participate in project activities. The CIL team also met with wheelchair users in regions throughout Georgia, including Ajara, Samegrelo, Guria, Imereti, Kakheti, Kutaisi, Ozurgeti, Chokkatauri and Zestafoni, as well as persons with mobility impairments living in the government institutions in Kutaisi and Senaki.

In addition to conducting activities with wheelchair-users in 3 cities, the 3 Teams increased public awareness of the problems facing wheelchair users through seminars, film festivals, barrier-removal projects and other public education activities in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi, all supporting the creation of a barrier-free environment. The DPO partners in these 3 cities created disability awareness and accessibility resource libraries in their offices and many media professionals, teachers, government officials, lawyers, and architects in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi learned about community access and barrier-removal issues. Project activities were often covered in national and local newspapers, radio and on TV.

Educating NGOs, Media Professionals, Architects, and Government Authorities: During project years 1-3 in each city, the 3 teams targeted key institutions of influence or responsibility for providing a barrier free environment and conducted meetings and round-table sessions for NGO staff, media professionals and journalists, school administrators, teachers and parents, architects, national and city government authorities, and the Georgian Orthodox Church in their communities on developing and implementing community-wide accessibility policies.

Recognizing the importance of the Georgian Orthodox Church in Georgian society and the potential afforded to reduce the isolation of persons with disabilities and increase awareness of church-goers, the CIL Team in Tbilisi met with His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II, the Patriarch of the Georgian Orthodox Church in March 2011. At this extraordinary and successful meeting with His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II, CIL representatives discussed public attitudes and requested the Patriarchate of Georgia to support efforts by PWD to improve the accessibility of the physical environment in Georgia and especially access to Churches. His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II is the current Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia and the spiritual leader of the Georgian Orthodox Church. He is officially styled as Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia, the Archbishop of Mtskheta-Tbilisi and Metropolitan bishop of Abkhazia and Pitsunda, His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II.

If the Church Patriarchate supports making roads, sidewalks and entrances to the Churches accessible, it would serve as a strong example for state or private actors to consider when they begin to address physical accessibility problems. The Patriarch promised to talk about and call for an accessible environment and for the inclusion of PWD in Churches in his sermons.

Among the many meetings held by the teams with municipal authorities to discuss improving accessibility, the CIL team met with the Head of the Transportation Department of Tbilisi City Hall to address parking and transportation issues, resulting in an agreement that at the first stage, 98 parking places would be arranged for disabled drivers in Tbilisi, and by the end of the year, every parking lot would be designed/modified to meet the standards of universal design.

Best Media Story And Poster Competition: In 2010, the 3 teams organized a competition for the best poster design on building an accessible community for all. The three winning poster designs were selected and disseminated as the best poster designs. A media competition was conducted in collaboration with another CIL project in March 2011. Elene Tsintsadze, a journalist from Palitra TV, won for the best disability story.

Publishing Brochures and a Newsletter: International best practices on how to create an accessible community were adapted, translated and disseminated to wheelchair users, architects, parents, activists, media professionals, and government authorities. International best practices for wheelchair mobility, maintenance, self-care, and barrier-free/accessible community materials were also translated into Georgian and disseminated. Also, the Tbilisi advocacy team produced and disseminated through the CIL website an accessible communities newsletter with updates.

Community Accessibility /Barrier Removal Micro-Projects:

The Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi teams, after identifying strategic accessibility barriers in their communities, each developed Community Accessibility/Barrier-Removal projects that would provide improved access for wheelchair users and persons with mobility impairments.

During the first 3 years of the project, the teams removed 12 barriers, including building ramps into schools, restaurants (co-financed with owners), parks and other public places, and making their own office bathrooms accessible. In May 2010, 3 mobile elections teams were equipped with a mini-van with a lift, portable ramps and RoughRider™ wheelchairs in order to assist voters with disabilities to reach their polling stations. This led to a new initiative in 2011, with support from IFES to improve elections access for citizens with disabilities who wished to vote

Another key meeting was with Disability Rights International regarding deinstitutionalization of persons with disabilities in Georgia. The CIL team also conducted a photo-monitoring project in 2011, showing barriers throughout Tbilisi with follow-up press conferences, leading some of the businesses and public facilities targeted to remove, partially remove or plan to remove barriers allowing wheelchair access.

Disability Film Exhibitions and Media Coverage: During the first 3 years, 7 small Disability Film Exhibitions, focused on active wheelchair users and community accessibility issues, were held or shown during project activities in the 3 cities to a wide variety of members of the community in order to positively raise their awareness about men, women and children who use wheelchairs and to promote an accessible community environment for wheelchair users.

The 3 Teams successfully solicited local TV, radio, and newspapers to cover the activities of the project and each city, with media covering project activities 35 times during the first 3 years. In addition, a 30-second radio PSA about wheelchairs and services available in Georgia was produced and broadcast on Radio 1, the national radio.

In early 2011, Tamta Sanikidze, a leading reporter from Imedi TV channel news program, “Chronicles,” contacted CIL to produce a program about the Public Defender's Report 2010 where, among other issues, the Public Defender's Office discusses the situation of disabled persons in Georgia. The program was broadcast on March 23, 2011 and was the first time any TV channel and news program in Georgia had ever led a broadcast on the topic of disability. Several public education videos promoting active lives for wheelchair users were produced and shown on CIL’s Facebook page, website and YouTube.

National Forum On Accessible Communities:

On December 2, 2009 World Disability Day, and again in 2010, A National Forum on Accessible Communities was organized with Georgian and US government authorities, lawmakers, professionals, public media, persons with mobility impairments and their families on the issues and lessons learned in Georgia and to discuss strategies for implementation national legislation promoting community accessibility for wheelchair users and persons with mobility impairments. In addition, the project helped organize 2 National Exhibitions in 2010.

In December 2011, the Tbilisi advocacy team combined a one-day wheelchair mobility skills event with the International Day of Persons with Disabilities, during which CIL had organized an outdoor “Solidarity Train” involving approximately 60 persons with disabilities and volunteers. Most of the participating wheelchair-users were in RoughRider™ wheelchairs.

The 2km long street demonstration ended in front of the Tbilisi Concert Hall, where a wheelchair obstacle course was set up and everyone, including long-time wheelchair users and non-disabled participants as well as onlookers, tried to overcome movement barriers of various difficulties in RoughRider™ wheelchairs. Five extra RoughRider™ were provided to volunteers by CIL for this public education event.

New USAID Advocacy Project

To further the momentum begun by this project, WID worked with CIL in the 12th quarter to develop and submit a proposal to USAID to strengthen and expand advocacy activities underway. CIL's proposal was ultimately funded, and advocacy activity under this separate and new USAID project began in 2012 in the western regions of Georgia.

USAID SUPPLEMENTARY FUNDING IN 2012

Extension Proposal Objective 1: To sustain and expand the capacity of the Georgian Wheelchair Production Network to sell, fit and distribute various models of over 3000 wheelchairs with cushions; increase the numbers of government vouchers for low-income wheelchair users; and increase humanitarian sales, fittings and dissemination of CIL wheelchair models

USAID supplementary funding in 2012 helped CIL to sustain and expand the capacity of the GWPN to sell, distribute and provide various models of wheelchairs with cushions.

New CIL Wheelchair Production Shop

A large building in Tbilisi was leased by CIL for a new wheelchair production facility. This building is located in a commercial neighborhood off of the main highway to the airport, approximately the same distance from the city center as the first wheelchair production shop but

in a different direction. CIL staff and contractors renovated the building and subdivided it into a raw materials storage room; a cutting room; a powder-coat paint and drying room; a general work and assembly area; two bathroom/showers and a separate office. The size of the new wheelchair production facility is approximately 450 m² compared to the 150 m² for the first

production shop. The newly renovated building also has an improved system for ventilation and used paint/color recycling and the amount of usable workspace is almost 3 times the size of the first wheelchair production shop. Wheelchair production was started up at the new building site in September 2012 and the production of wheelchairs has continued in the building ever since.

New RoughRider™ Children's Wheelchair

In 2012, CIL introduced a new 12-inch wide children's wheelchair. This new children's wheelchair is lightweight and provides more options for postural support seating.

New RoughRider™ Electric Wheelchair

In September 2012, WID's project director, Mr. Curtis, created a prototype electric wheelchair using a new RoughRider™ wheelchair model created in Georgia with greatly reduced armrests. This new model makes it much easier to transfer in and out of the wheelchair by quadriplegics, women with disabilities and others with limited physical strength. This newly designed Georgian RoughRider™ wheelchair frame was outfitted with 2 motor-in-the-hub wheels from China, along with a lithium-ion battery and a joystick controller. WWI staff provided technical support for attaching the wheels, battery and controller to the wheelchair frame. The electric RoughRider™ wheelchair was determined to be highly functional and was field-tested in the U.S., Georgia and Morocco.

These electric bicycle technology components were purchased from a Chinese business identified through the Internet with the electric wheelchair conversion kit costing less than \$1,000. The CIL electric RoughRider™ wheelchair is foldable, lightweight at 35kg and travels at the speed of a fast walk. The battery, the controller and the wheels are easily removable for easy storage in a car trunk. It is highly maneuverable over rough terrain and one battery charge enables traveling for 11 km. The RoughRider™ electric wheelchair prototype received an enthusiastic reception from various Georgians wheelchair-users.

In February 2013, Mr. Afonin worked with CIL wheelchair designers, Levan Talakhadze and Tamaz Injgia, continuing the process of developing a prototype of an electric power add-on to

the Whirlwind RoughRider™ wheelchair. CIL bought three electric wheelchair conversion kits from China and constructed 2 more electric wheelchairs. Everyone recognized that an inexpensive electric wheelchair is a very promising new technology product for CIL, and the electric RoughRider™ wheelchair, proven in concept in the streets of Georgia, has a good potential for future profit from government sales.

In March 2013, Mr. Afonin and CIL wheelchair designer Levan Talakhadze spent 2 weeks in San Francisco participating in a wheelchair design team at the WWI shop led by Matt McCambridge and included Ralf Hotchkiss, Aaron Wieler, Alexander Afonin, Levan Talakhadze and WID consultant Salam Hassan, a wheelchair user from Iraq who has extensive experience in wheelchair building, electronics and computer engineering. Mr. Hassan also provided expert advice on battery issues and on the programming of the joystick controller unit. The wheelchair design team first supported the modification of the RoughRider™ axle block for the CIL electric RoughRider™ wheelchair production only.

For the electric RoughRider™ wheelchair, the first big technical issue solved was an easy attachment and quick release of the large diameter axle of the Chinese motor-in-hub wheels to the basic RoughRider™ wheelchair. Prior to the San Francisco workshop, Mr. Afonin had designed a quick release mechanism for the motor-in-hub wheels in Georgia. Photographs and video of this quick release mechanism were shown to the team and everyone was very positive about the simplicity and durability of this first prototype. A second technical issue was a need for anti-tip wheels behind the electric wheelchair in order to protect the wheelchair user from accidentally falling over backwards. The team examined several WWI anti-tip wheel designs and prototypes and an anti-tip wheel design was chosen and installed on the electric RoughRider™ wheelchair prototype in San Francisco, where the hub motor axle is attached in the middle axle block position. These anti-tip wheels functioned correctly on the electric wheelchair prototype in San Francisco.

Mr. Talakhadze later created another electric RoughRider™ wheelchair prototype in Georgia with the axle hub attachment placed 40 mm behind the final axle hole of the RoughRider™ wheelchair. Field-testing of this electric wheelchair in Georgia demonstrated that it is able to go up very steep ramps (steep ramps with incline ratios greater than accessibility standards) without tipping over backwards. Following 6 months of prototyping and evaluation, CIL began producing 30 electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs and also provided assessment, postural seating services, individual orientation, training and maintenance for each electric wheelchair user and/or parent.

For Mr. Talakhadze, this was the first time he had been involved with a professional wheelchair design team, and he came away from the experience with a better understanding and appreciation for the importance of following a formal wheelchair design process that does not cut corners to avoid future problems. Mr. Talakhadze also learned more about feature design specifications and about how to describe and communicate specifications to those workers who will be implementing the designs. The wheelchair design team workshop in San Francisco was a rich experience for Mr. Talakhadze, which is already yielding positive results in his follow-up work in Georgia on the electric power add-on RoughRider™ wheelchair. After returning home, Mr. Talakhadze was promoted to production engineer at the CIL wheelchair production shop.

Improving the Electric RoughRider™ Wheelchair

WWI consultant, Alexander Afonin, in September 2013 made a MAJOR improvement in the fixture for making the part that allows the wheels with motors in their hubs to be easily and quickly put on and taken off the RoughRider™ wheelchair. The improvement guarantees that the part will always fit exactly, no matter which worker is making the part and that CIL's RoughRider™ wheelchair can operate either as a manual wheelchair or as a power wheelchair.

The electric power add-on unit for the RoughRider™ wheelchair now makes it possible for many more people to benefit from RoughRider™ wheelchair technology and will open up an important new market for CIL wheelchair products. The new electric RoughRider™ wheelchair will allow severely disabled persons to become more independent and participate in social activities.

Already the Georgian government has ordered 34 of these electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs and the US military has ordered 35 of these electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs at a price that will guarantee a profit margin for CIL.

Improving the RoughRider™ Wheelchair

WWI's, Marc Krizack, joined Alexander Afonin, WID's Bruce Curtis, CIL's Giorgi Dzneladze and Levan Talakhadze and WID consultant Stefan Constantinescu in September 2013 for a final review of the wheelchair production business. The final review process also included a look at

what additional products CIL should manufacture in the future. It was 100% agreed that despite the great benefits of the current RoughRider™ wheelchair, it would be better if its weight was significantly reduced on basic design criteria for moving forward with a new lightweight RoughRider™ model. It was agreed that CIL would have the right to manufacture and sell the new lightweight wheelchair, without having to pay any royalties, in exchange for its contributions during the lightweight wheelchair design process. The next step will be made by WWI raising funds for the design and prototyping of the lightweight RoughRider™ wheelchair.

Government Budget for Disability

The government budget for disability in 2011 was 6,671,100 GEL of which 196,000 GEL was for wheelchairs and 656,700 GEL for children's habilitation/rehabilitation program (NDC falls under this category). The total disability budget increased in 2014 and reached 9,517,000 GEL of which 279,000 GEL is for wheelchairs and 1,209,000 GEL for children's rehabilitation program, an increase of 70% for wheelchair purchase and provision and 54% for the children's habilitation/rehabilitation program.

In 2011, CIL was effective in convincing government authorities to begin increasing the number of wheelchair vouchers as well as to construct a government tender and selection process, which favored Georgian businesses producing wheelchairs. CIL also educated the government authorities about the importance of requiring wheelchair provision according to WHO guidelines (assessment, fitting and training). Due to these educational efforts and the adoption of these policies by the government authorities in August 2013, CIL no longer has competitors for the government wheelchair tender and services almost all of the wheelchair voucher customers.

Further increasing the government budget for meeting the current need of adults and children wheelchair users for an appropriate wheelchair, according to WHO wheelchair provision guidelines, will take additional time. Therefore, CIL is trying to increase sales from large institutional customers as well as from individuals through public advertising and innovative quality guarantees, support services and buy back offers.

CIL Negotiations with the Ministry of Health Voucher Program

CIL decided, as a negotiating tactic, to stop producing wheelchairs between April - September 2013 due to the low payment amount provided by the Ministry of Health voucher program for providing assessments, wheelchairs and follow-up services. The low amount of money provided by the Ministry voucher program for each wheelchair was clearly making CIL's production business non-profitable and unsustainable. The amount paid by the voucher program did not even cover the complete cost of CIL manufacturing their RoughRider™ wheelchair and did not pay for the additional work of providing a client assessment or for delivering the wheelchair to the client/user. CIL conducted intense discussions over several months with the Deputy Minister of Health in order to increase the amount of money paid by the government voucher program for CIL's wheelchairs and provision services.

The Deputy Minister of Health at that time was appointed by the previous government and political party and directly responsible for managing the prices and items covered by government tenders and the voucher system. Mr. Dzneladze met many times with this Deputy Minister and strongly requested that they increase the amount of money paid by the government under the

voucher program for manual wheelchairs. After a meeting of the National Disability Council in June 2013, in which Mr. Dzeladze publicly discussed his problems with the current government pricing for wheelchairs under the voucher system, the Prime Minister directed Ministry of Health officials to research and evaluate the pricing of wheelchairs and other disability services under the Ministry of Health voucher program. CIL staff collaborated with the Ministry of Health in their research and evaluation efforts in order to establish a new government voucher price for wheelchairs.

Pressure Relieving Wheelchair Cushions

After several years of unreliable suppliers and foam quality issues, CIL ordered and received 300 DDO Slim pressure relief cushions in March 2014, which had been field-tested in Georgia, at a significantly lower cost than Georgian made pressure relief cushions and will make them available as standard equipment on CIL wheelchairs whenever needed. Mr. Noon recommended that approximately 100 cushions be tracked for problems through a simplified questionnaire (approximately 5 questions), which will be provided through mail or phone. It is recommended that, although adequate pressure relieving cushions can be ordered from DDO, it is still important for Georgian providers and suppliers to maintain the ability to produce pressure relief cushions. To demonstrate continuing local production capacity, a post-project plan has been developed that includes CIL ordering new high quality foam from sources in Turkey.

Wheelchair Repair Shops in Gori and Zugdidi

In December 2011, Joni Gergedava from Zugdidi and Malkhaz Ioramashvili from Gori were trained in wheelchair mechanics, Basic assessment and participated in other project advocacy activities until the shops were set-up in the 13th Quarter. In September 2012, CIL provided equipment and tools to the wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi and purchased wheelchair parts and bearings for the wheelchair mechanics to use while providing repair services to local wheelchair users.

The wheelchair repair shops in Gori (left) and Zugdidi (right)

By September 2012, a wheelchair repair shop was built into the building owned and operated by the GDC and was in operation. In addition to repairing wheelchairs, the Gori team is planning to produce special assistive sticks to reach for things and hand controls for vehicles. Also by September 2012, the Zugdidi wheelchair repair shop, located in a garage behind the Association

DEA office, was cleaned, remodeled and in operation. By the end of the project, the wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi provided wheelchair repairs for 107 clients.

Welding Training for Regional Wheelchair Repair Mechanics

WID suggested to CIL and the Gori and Zugdidi regional partners that providing welding torches and basic welding skills to the wheelchair repair mechanics, could add some additional commercial business, which could bring in a small amount of income to help sustain the wheelchair mechanics and repair services.

In March 2014, CIL purchased welding torches for Gori and Zugdidi wheelchair repair shops and conducted a 3-day training in welding for wheelchair mechanics Malkhaz Ioramashvili from Gori and Joni Gergedava from Zugdidi. The wheelchair mechanics were trained in basic welding skills by CIL welders on CIL welding equipment as well as their new welding torches. CIL agreed to continue providing technical assistance to the regional teams through telephone and online communication as well as on-site visits and advice.

Training in Micro-Business Management for Regional Wheelchair Repair Mechanics

CIL is also working with International Organization of Migration (IOM) Georgian office to provide training in micro-business management to Gori and Zugdidi wheelchair repair staff. IOM is currently implementing a training program for mine victims teaching them basic business management and financial accounting skills and has already agreed to include Joni Gergedava (who is a mine victim) from Zugdidi and Malkhaz Ioramashvili and Ito Karkishvili from Gori in the next training in micro-business management to be conducted during late Spring 2014.

Other Products Produced by the Shop

The CIL wheelchair production shop produces and sells, in addition to wheelchairs and seating cushions, metal folding ramps, car hand controls, metal accessible parking signs and other assistive mobility products for wheelchair users. CIL helped to increase the participation of persons with disabilities in elections by providing foldable metal ramps, constructed by the CIL wheelchair production shop, for key voting sites and by using their wheelchair accessible lift van, portable metal ramps and election assistants to help transport wheelchair users to their election stations on Election Day.

Wheelchair Provision and Screening Training for Social Workers

CIL has adopted a long-term strategy to expand the availability of wheelchair provision services throughout Georgia and to be able to collect correct information about wheelchair users (their wheelchair needs, measurements, etc.) by training and utilizing professional Social Workers in cities and regions that are employed by the Ministry of Health and stationed throughout Georgian rural and urban neighborhoods. They work on the front lines of families with social needs throughout Georgian society and often become aware of individuals who have physical disabilities and individuals who need a wheelchair. At the end of the 3rd year of the project, CIL began conducting periodic one-day workshops for social workers on basic disability awareness and information about the quality and mobility differences between various models of wheelchairs including the RoughRider™ wheelchair.

In March 2014, CIL and NDC OTs, with input from WID and Jamie Noon, developed a more substantive curriculum and conducted a one-day model training for social workers from West Georgia, on how to identify the needs of wheelchair users and how to screen them for an appropriate wheelchair. CIL worked with the National Social Service Agency to identify capable and willing social workers interested in learning more about how to work with wheelchair users and to help with identifying their measurements and needs for a wheelchair.

Social Workers from 8 cities, Kutaisi, Sachkhere, Mestia, Martvili, Ozurgeti, Zugdidi, Poti and Batumi attended the training conducted by CIL and NDC wheelchair service providers (Levan Talakhadze, Nino Rukhadze and Ilo Volkashov). The training covered the following topics: Overview of wheelchair users and their needs; Wheelchairs available in Georgia (show/explain basic/intermediate/advance products; show/explain wheelchair types and parts; show/explain/practice safe wheelchair use; try different sizes and types); Basic Assessment Services available in Georgia (service levels: pre/basic/intermediate/advanced; Service training available; Show/explain/practice measuring with caliper); Pressure sore prevention and care; Practice screening and provision (small group work with roleplaying).

As the training evaluation form demonstrated, by the end of the training the majority of the Social Workers felt confident enough to determine which service level was appropriate for potential wheelchair recipients as well as how to take their basic body measurements for screening and to refer them to professional service providers if a higher level of service was needed. The Social Worker training topics also included information about Georgian and international legal acts and regulations dealing with persons with disabilities and a brainstorming session on how to integrate wheelchair service provision into the current system of social work in Georgia. It was noted by the Social Workers that legislation changes were needed in order to

improve the professional services provided by them. Finally, all of the Social Worker trainees expressed willingness and readiness for additional training in wheelchair provision service levels.

Marketing: CIL Public Showroom for Wheelchairs

In March 2014, CIL decided that trying to remodel and construct a public showroom for wheelchairs at the new wheelchair factory was not cost-effective and, more importantly, the location of the new wheelchair factory was not convenient for the public to visit by car or public transportation since it is located near the airport. Therefore, CIL decided to rent a wheelchair products and accessories exhibition space, within a medical product and supply business, currently located across the street from the main hospital complex. CIL staff is scheduled daily to be at this public showroom with examples of CIL manual and power wheelchairs, pressure relief cushions and metal ramps for the public to buy.

Extension Proposal Objective 2: To fully implement plans to institutionalize the training system of Georgian OTs as postural support seating specialists and to sustain the NDC provision of postural support seating for children in wheelchairs.

Postural Support Seating Products and Services

Supplementary funding has allowed the project partners to implement and institutionalize in the Georgia State University training system for OTs, the WHO Basic and Intermediate level services. NDC occupational therapists and OT students continued to be trained and certified according to WHO Guidelines in the skills and knowledge to assess, prescribe, and produce high quality, low cost adaptive postural support seating for adults and children who use wheelchairs using locally available materials. By the 5th year of the project, WID, Jamie Noon and NDC had also institutionalized the production of seating support equipment and wheelchair vendor relationships, quality control, and the documentation of client satisfaction with the provision of service. NDC has continued to educate government authorities, professionals, families and the public media about the current availability of adult and children support seating services offered by NDC. During project years 4 and 5, NDC:

- Continued to provide an ongoing clinic for Occupational Therapists (OT) to provide WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services;
- Continued to provide the WHO Wheelchair Service Training Package, Basic and Intermediate levels, in the OT training course at Georgia State University;
- Exceeded the planned numbers of OT specialists to be trained in the project;
- Exceeded the planned number of adults and children who have received postural support seating services and mobility devices; and
- Increased public demand for government vouchers to pay for these services.

Independent Practice Cases for all Practical Courses

After completing the 5-day Basic course and 10-day Intermediate course, each training participant completed a minimum of 3 client cases of independent practice in order to be certified for each WHO course level. For the 10 day Advanced course, each participant was required to complete a minimum of 5 client cases of independent practice in order to be certified.

WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced Training Classes

NDC certified trainers conducted the following trainings in project years 4 and 5: Advanced in April 2012 (2 women completed the training); Basic in April 2012 (5 women and 2 men completed the training); Basic in October 2012 (4 women completed the training); Basic in July 2013 (5 women and 1 man completed the training); Intermediate in October 2013 (4 women completed the training); and Advanced in March 2014 (5 women completed the training).

International Expert Training

In mid 2012, Mr. Noon arranged for additional expert training for 2 Georgia OTs in the U.S. and in 2013 these 2 Georgian OTs contributed their expertise to the USAID working group on appropriate wheelchair services. In addition, the Georgian OT master trainers, who are also the senior instructors for Occupational Therapy students at the Georgian State University, were responsible for the integration of the WHO WSTP (Wheelchair Service Training Package) at the Basic level into the OT training course at Georgia State University. They provided feedback to the USAID working group, during an international call, on their experience of providing instruction to OT students.

Static Seating Chairs and Postural Support Equipment

In March 2013, Mr. Kakushadze stated that NDC makes special tables and chairs (Static Seating Chairs) for children and that sometimes these special tables and chairs also need to be adapted with postural supports and pressure relieving cushions.

Both Mr. Noon and WID agreed that it is not essential that posture support seating be provided only in a wheelchair for it to count as a service result of this project. Mr. Kakushadze was

advised that he could add postural support equipment and pressure relieving cushions to the static seating tables and chairs, which are being prescribed by the OT's for disabled children and these statistics have been included under the OTHER category along with assessment and posture support statistics provided on the indicator form.

WHO Basic and Intermediate Services in the Regions

In early 2011, NDC began to educate medical professionals and families in other regions by providing an outreach seating service clinic every six months with visits by NDC occupational therapists for assessment and postural seating solutions in order to meet the need for these services outside the capital of Tbilisi. USAID supplementary funding in 2012 helped NDC to sustain and expand the regional outreach seating service clinics.

For example, NDC completed a regional wheelchair assessment activity in Zugdidi (Samegrelo). A trained and certified team of OTs provided a basic level assessment for adults and children previously identified who needed support to sit upright in their wheelchairs (this regional assessment activity was supervised by Jamie Noon).

Their first step was to conduct an individual assessment. They interviewed and measured each client, with the participation of their parent/relative, in order to analyze what type of body support would be most useful for improving how they sit upright in their wheelchairs. The OT team also examined the client's current wheelchair to determine if it is possible to continue using their current wheelchair with the attached posture supports or if it will be better for the client to receive a new RoughRider™ wheelchair along with their new posture supports.

The OT team's second step was to return later to Zugdidi for a second visit with all of the posture support components and if necessary, with a new wheelchair and correctly fit/adjust the support components onto the wheelchair so that it improved the seating posture of the client. The provision of postural seating services every six months in regional cities has only begun to meet the needs of adult and children wheelchair users throughout Georgia. After discussions with NDC in April 2014, government authorities stated that they were willing to include funds in the government budget for purchasing some postural support seating services through the State voucher program.

Sustainability of Postural Support Services

Both CIL and NDC have been advocating for the Government to include funds for WHO Intermediate Services provision within the State voucher program. In March 2013, Mr. Kakushadze of NDC was informed that the WHO assessments and postural support services had been included in the *State Disability Action Plan 2013-2016*. Unfortunately, money to pay for these services was not included in the State budget funding for 2014. In May 2014, Mr. Kakushadze met with the Social Affairs Agency officials at the Ministry of Labor, Health and Social Affairs who expressed hope that NDC would receive funding from the Ministry to provide the full range of Postural Support Services to 10 people per month from the State budget in 2014-2015. This would more than cover the costs that the project expended on these services over a similar period of time. However, there has been no decision made as of this report.

Extension Proposal Objective 3: To remove access barriers at important religious, historical and natural sites.

Community Accessibility, Public Education And Advocacy Team Seminars

During the 15th and 18th quarters, Disability Advocacy Team members received group training to increase their advocacy skills, how to develop barrier removal projects and pressure sore prevention and care.

Community Barrier Removal and Accessibility

The number of access barriers removed during the project was smaller than planned because the amount of project funds provided to each advocacy team (\$500 for each barrier removal project) was not sufficient to begin and finish each barrier removal project. All of the advocacy teams were required to find matching money in order to complete each barrier removal project and the teams were not always successful in their efforts to find matching money.

Also the negotiation, planning and construction process for each barrier removal project was often much longer and more complicated than planned, which slowed down and reduced the total completion numbers. Although the actual number of barriers removed was smaller than planned, the project targeted certain institutions like Banks, Government offices, Election voting sites and the Georgian Orthodox Church, which in turn have made independent and ongoing efforts to increase accessibility at sites under their control.

The CIL advocacy team also consulted on making key Tbilisi tourist destinations accessible for wheelchair-users including the National Cathedral; the Funicular tramway station to Mtatsminda

Park (CIL has built a ramp at the lower station that allows wheelchair users to enter the tram and also installed a platform lift on the upper station); the renovation of Old Tbilisi neighborhood; the main street of Rusateveli Ave. (construction almost finished); and the Georgian National Museum. In addition, CIL is currently working with City Hall to adapt the cable car station that takes people up to Narikala Castle in Old Tbilisi.

Community Accessibility, Public Education Activities and Events

During project years 4 and 5, the Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi teams conducted empowerment and rights workshops for persons with disabilities and their families and recruited them to participate in project activities including mobility skills workshops and public education events.

The 3 teams also educated persons with disabilities in their communities about their right to an accessible environment and their right to vote. The 3 teams also reached out to IDPs with disabilities and persons with disabilities in the surrounding rural villages.

During years 4-5, the Gori and Zugdidi teams conducted an accessibility assessment of public buildings in their municipalities. In each city, the 3 Teams continued to target key institutions of influence or responsible for providing a barrier free environment and conducted meetings and Round-table sessions for NGO staff, media professionals and journalists, school administrators,

teachers and parents, architects, national and city government authorities, and the Georgian Orthodox Church in their communities on developing and implementing community-wide accessibility policies.

Recognize my disabilities, emphasize my possibilities
ნუ შეშლუდავ, ხაზი გაუსვი ჩემს შესაძლებლობებს

CIL conducted a Media Competition on “Promoting Accessible Elections” aimed at making the public debates on the rights of PWDs more publicly active by encouraging the involvement of journalists. 2 winners were awarded certificates and prizes (TV sets) on January 31, 2013. CIL conducted a poster competition on accessible environment and barrier-free mobility for wheelchair users. Giorgi Oganov, a student at Tbilisi State University, won the poster competition and 275 copies were printed and disseminated.

Event for U.S. Assistant Secretary of State Nuland

In December 2013, during her visit to Georgia, Assistant Secretary of State Victoria Nuland met with CIL representatives as well as Government dignitaries. Along with Prime Minister Irakli

Gharibashvili and Minister of Defense Irakli Alasania, Ms. Nuland attended the public opening ceremony for the State Chancellery wheelchair ramp, which was built by the CIL Tbilisi advocacy team with financial assistance from USAID. Ms. Nuland expressed special gratitude to CIL for years of work, commitment and dedication to solving disability issues and for sparing no effort to improve the lives of PWD in Georgia adding, “CIL has recently hosted a high-level Government event dedicated to the International Disability Day, which was attended by the Prime Minister and an impressive number of the country’s highest officials. However, there’s still more to do.” Two days after this high-level meeting, the Government of Georgia approved the “Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for

Persons with Disabilities,” according to which, all Government buildings must be made accessible for persons with disabilities.

National Day of the Rights of PWD in Georgia Wheelchair Dance FLASHMOB

The Tbilisi team celebrated National Day of the Rights of PWD in Georgia with a Solidarity Sports Campaign in front of the Parliament of Georgia involving wheelchair users and Members of the Parliament (MPs) in Kutaisi, June 12, 2013. The next day in Tbilisi, CIL mobilized a wheelchair dance FLASHMOB to raise public awareness on disability, promote the rights of PWD and motivate the youth with disabilities to be more active and independent. 12 able-bodied professional dancers in wheelchairs, including 4 wheelchair users, participated in the dancing FLASHMOB (freestyle dance) in front of Rustaveli Metro Station in June 2013.

This was the first time a FLASHMOB with wheelchair users was organized in Georgia.

The FLASHMOB dance near the metro station completely stopped people and passers-by were watching the wheelchair dance with great interest, due to which the dancers had to repeat the dance and performed again in front of the inspired audience. It was also extraordinary that one of the most popular TV stations in Georgia, Imedi TV, transmitted the FLASHMOB live. The Ministry of Sports and Youth Affairs of Georgia also sponsored and supported the FLASHMOB event along with CIL member DPO, Movement for Accessible Environment, and the only radio

program on disability, “We Are Here” (Radio Imedi). In addition, almost all of the leading TV stations and Internet media outlets covered the FLASHMOB event.

Meeting with Georgian Wounded Warriors in Washington, DC

In July 2013, CIL staff and WID project director Mr. Curtis visited 6 Georgian soldiers wounded in Afghanistan undergoing rehabilitation treatment at Walter Reed Hospital in Washington, DC.

CIL discussed with the soldiers the organizations and services available to disabled Georgians, as they had no idea that there were disability organizations and services in Georgia, as well as the new RoughRider™ wheelchairs, both manual and electric, produced by CIL with 50% disabled factory workers. CIL encouraged the soldiers to visit the wheelchair factory and meet with CIL and its members when they returned to Georgia.

After returning to Georgia and as a follow-up, CIL was contacted by the Ministry of Defense Medical Department officials in Georgia to discuss issues of accommodating the needs of disabled Georgian warriors, in general, from their psychosocial rehabilitation to the adaptation of their living homes. There have been several meetings since between CIL and Ministry of Defense to discuss ongoing details of cooperation. CIL continues working with the Ministry of Defense around these issues and has confirmed their readiness to offer CIL’s knowledge; experiences, resources, technology and methodology to make sure that the needs and requirements of these wounded soldiers are completely met.

National Forum

CIL marked the International Day of Persons with Disabilities activities by convening a disability conference, “Persons with Disabilities – Current Situation and New Challenges” dedicated to December 3, the International Day of Persons with Disabilities, which took place on November 30, 2012 at the Courtyard Marriott Hotel. The purpose of the Disability Conference was to review the disability situation in the country, discuss and agree upon future approaches and cooperation with authorities, DPOs and stakeholder NGOs; emphasize the importance of PWD integration into the society and demonstrate Georgian and U.S. government support for protecting the rights of PWDs.

Giorgi Dzneladze (left), Prime Minister Bidzina Ivanishvili (center), and U.S. Ambassador Richard Norland (right)

More than 150 people from governmental and non-governmental local and international organizations attended the Disability Conference on November 30. What’s most important, the Conference was representational of highest authorities from the Government of Georgia and the US Embassy/USAID Mission. Namely, the Conference was attended by Bidzina Ivanishvili, the Prime Minister of Georgia; Giorgi Margvelashvili, Minister of Education and Science; Nodar Khaduri, Minister of Finance; Tea Tsulukiani, Minister of

Justice; Davit Narmania, Minister of Regional Development and Infrastructure; Davit Sergenko, Minister of Labour, Healthcare and Social Affairs; US Ambassador Richard Norland, USAID Mission Director Stephen M. Haykin; leaders of disabled people’s organizations, representatives of human rights organizations, Public Defender’s Office, media professionals and other stakeholders.

On December 3, CIL marked the International Day of Persons with Disabilities activities by convening a cabinet-level disability event involving the Prime Minister, US Ambassador, Ministers and directors of various Georgian and international organizations and missions, PWD, Wounded Warrior Program representatives and media professionals. Two days after this high-level meeting, the Government of Georgia approved the *Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for Persons with Disabilities*, according to which, all Government buildings must be made accessible for persons with disabilities, starting after December 3, 2013.

Public Education Materials, Media Coverage and Use of Social Media

CIL produced a brochure on accessibility of tourist sites for both a Georgia and international audience. CIL also produced a 5-7 minute video about social etiquette and ways of communication with wheelchair users, including basic wheelchair mobility skills, broadcast on Public TV 1 in November-December 2012 and a television PSA informing the public about how people needing wheelchairs can access government voucher funding, broadcast on Public TV 1 in early 2013. The 3 advocacy teams also posted access and parking signage at designated spaces in their cities.

A total of 96 media spots covered project activities and raised awareness of disability issues targeted by the project. CIL and the other advocacy teams made extensive use of social media, including Facebook and posting YouTube videos, in order to organize, mobilize and educate persons with disabilities and the general public.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills Training of Trainers

Supplementary funding allowed WID to again hire AR expert Tomasz Tasiemski, PhD in order to conduct a Training of Trainers workshop for 5 Georgian trainers who use wheelchairs (3 men and 2 women) in wheelchair mobility skills (basic and advanced); activities of daily living;

wheelchair sports competitions; weight training; wheelchair outing; lectures on wheelchair adjustment, post-SCI medical complications, prevention of pressure sores, sexuality and fertility. The first three days of training was dedicated to individual Training Of Trainers and the next three days were used for practice by the Georgian team. Under the supervision of Mr. Tasiemski, the 5 Georgian trainers practiced by teaching mobility skills to 10 students of Social Work.

One-Day Wheelchair Mobility Skills Workshops

The community advocacy teams in Gori and Zugdidi also continued to offer 1-day wheelchair mobility, maintenance and repair and self-care survival skills events to reach a greater number of

local wheelchair users. The Gori team held their events in parks and natural settings in the surrounding areas, combining the workshop with an outdoor excursion and barbeque picnic for wheelchair users that generally do not have the opportunity or transportation to visit these locations. The teams conducted 10 events for more than 100 wheelchair users during project years 4 and 5.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills Camps

CIL and 3 Georgian wheelchair mobility skills trainers (1 male and 2 female wheelchair users trained by Dr. Tasiemski), organized and led the 3rd 5-day wheelchair mobility skills training camp in June 2013 and the 4th in October 2013. Both were held in the same facilities as previous events, the Senaki Hotel Ia. Camps was used artificial obstacles for a wheelchair mobility course and equipment for wheelchair games were also provided. 14 wheelchair users (7 men and 7 women) participated in the June camp in Q17 and 17 wheelchair-riders (12 men and 5 women) participated in the October camp in Q19. In addition, there were able-bodied assistants, an archery instructor and a nurse supporting camp activities. In addition to learning essential independent living skills and wheelchair mobility techniques, a major focus again was on sports activities, during which participants competed with each other in basketball, archery and various wheelchair games. There were outings in the center of Batumi at the end of the camp, during which all of the participants divided into small groups and had different tasks to fulfill that demonstrated both accessibility and inaccessibility of the local physical environment and allowed them to test and practice their new skills in a real-life situation.

Some wheelchair users who were in the camp had not left their homes for years due to both the lack of wheelchair mobility skills as well as psychological barriers and the fear of being laughed at by society. By the end of the camp, it became obvious that these individuals had overcome their most fearful barriers; become motivated to leave their home; desired to become more integrated; and they all made promises that they would continue living active lives in the future.

One of the camp participants, Lasha Lomidze (a veteran from the 2008 August war between Georgia and Russia and a wheelchair user from the Sachkhere, Imereti Region), has been introduced to the Georgian Paralympic Committee as a promising power-lifter. Mr. Lomidze is now in a training course to prepare for local and international disability sports competitions.

Future President of Georgia Visits Mobility Skills Camp

On October 7, 2013, Georgia Dream presidential candidate, Giorgi Margvelashvili, visited the wheelchair mobility skills training camp held in the Hotel Ia in Senaki. Mr. Margvelashvili met with persons with disabilities participating in the camp in order to hear about their issues. The presidential candidate also tried his hand at navigating a wheelchair over obstacles and later told the camp participants that if he won the upcoming election, the President's administration would have a special representative dealing with the issues of citizens with disabilities. Mr. Margvelashvili also mentioned that the government was working on issues facing PWD and planning to make legislative changes. Later that October, Mr. Margvelashvili was elected President of Georgia.

Pressure Sore Prevention and Care

During 2013 and 2014, WID and CIL worked on promoting pressure sore prevention and on creating a medical treatment program with the Ministry of Health. In 2013, CIL and WID representatives held a meeting with 2 Georgian surgeons to discuss this very serious problem, and CIL conducted negotiations with an Armenian specialist in pressure sore surgery to visit Georgia, conduct at least 10 surgeries and to have Georgian doctors attend the surgeries and learn successful medical techniques from him. The Armenian surgeon, Mr. Artak Oganessian, visited Tbilisi in December 2013, during which he also met with 2 Georgian doctors and evaluated the conditions of several patients awaiting surgery. He also visited two Georgian hospitals (Ghudushauri and the Patriarchate's clinics) where the pressure sore medical care program will be implemented (surgery and post-surgery rehabilitation). At the same time, CIL began working with the Healthcare Ministry to develop a Government program on pressure sore prevention and medical treatment, which is already described in the *2014-2016 State Action Plan on Providing Equal Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities*.

In March 2014, CIL received official agreement from the Ministry of Health to allocate funds for the surgeries and the travel of Dr. Oganessian from Armenia. Currently, the Ministry has agreed to pay for 7 surgeries for those individuals who are in the most critical condition, but CIL is also working with the Ministry to increase funding and to pay for the surgeries of other people who are on a waiting list.

The September 2013 advocacy team seminar and the March 2014 Social Workers training in western Georgia included Pressure Sore Prevention and Care as a key topic.

c. Results achieved

Original Proposal Objective 1: To establish a national network for the production, repair and distribution of wheelchairs and other mobility assistance and adaptive equipment.

Extension Proposal Objective 1: To sustain and expand the capacity of the Georgian Wheelchair Production Network to sell, fit and distribute various models of over 3000 wheelchairs with cushions; increase the numbers of government vouchers for low-income wheelchair users; and increase humanitarian sales, fittings and dissemination of CIL wheelchair models.

Network of Wheelchair Production, Outreach, Sales, Distribution and Repair Shops

Beginning in 2009, WID and our 4 Georgian NGO partners established the **Georgian Wheelchair Production Network**, which is today supported by: (1) a sustainable wheelchair production and repair business in Tbilisi, which produces and sells an adult and child model of the manual RoughRider™ indoor-outdoor wheelchair; an electric version of the RoughRider™ wheelchair; comfort and pressure relief wheelchair cushions; metal folding ramps; car hand controls and other assistive mobility products for Georgian wheelchair users; (2) a Postural Support Seating Service, according to WHO guidelines, provided by trained and certified (WHO Intermediate Services) OTs at clinics held at NDC and every 6 months in regional cities; (3) the local production of pressure relief cushions in the city of Gori; and (4) small wheelchair repair shops in the cities of Gori and Zugdidi.

CIL has achieved the business and managerial capacity to produce and market high quality, low cost wheelchairs for adults and children using locally available and imported materials. The 5 wheelchair riders, who currently work at the wheelchair production shop and who had no previous experience in manufacturing prior to this project, have now been trained and know how to perform their jobs well enough to be able to work effectively in order to meet demanding production deadlines. Wheelchair repair mechanics have also been trained in the skills and knowledge to repair wheelchairs and have been established in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi. CIL staff has been trained on how to implement sales, marketing and public education plans and how to identify and secure international funding in order to sustain their wheelchair sales.

By the end of the five-year project, **CIL has slightly exceeded its production target of 3,000 RoughRider™ wheelchairs. During the project, 1,928 RoughRider™ wheelchairs were purchased through the Georgian government’s voucher program or by the U.S. government (1,859 manual and 69 electric). CIL has also sold more than 1,000 wheelchairs to humanitarian assistance organizations (UNHCR, UNICEF, ICRC, the LDS Church), municipalities, a hospital and to purchasers in Armenia.**

New Government Tender for Purchasing Wheelchairs and Government Budget for Disability

The government budget for disability in 2011 was 6,671,100 GEL of which 196,000 GEL was for wheelchairs and 656,700 GEL for children's habilitation/rehabilitation program (NDC falls under this category). The total disability budget increased in 2014 and reached 9,517,000 GEL of which 279,000 GEL is for wheelchairs and 1,209,000 GEL for children's rehabilitation program. **This represents an increase of the government budget of 70% for wheelchair purchase and provision and an increase of 54% for the children’s habilitation/rehabilitation program.**

In August 2013, CIL succeeded in negotiations with the Ministry of Labor, Healthcare and Social Affairs to change the government policy on wheelchair provision tenders in order to bring the government tender qualifications into compliance with modern international standards and World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines on wheelchair provision. As a result of 6 months of CIL meetings and discussions with MoLHSA, the Government of Georgia issued a new resolution on wheelchair provision on August 22, 2013, according to which, **starting from September 1, 2013, there will be a new separate state program for purchasing wheelchairs (both manual and electric) called, “Supporting Local Wheelchair Production and**

Employment of PWD.” This Government of Georgia amendment sets out eligibility criteria according to which only those local wheelchair providers are eligible to provide wheelchairs within the state program, who **produce wheelchairs locally; employ PWD in their production; and have all the technical and human capacity, technology and methodology to follow the WHO guidelines on wheelchair provision, which requires basic assessment and fitting, training, technical and postural support seating service, when needed.**

This new resolution also requires that Georgia adhere to the international standards for wheelchair production and service outlined in the World Health Organization’s *Guidelines on the Provision of Manual Wheelchairs in less resourced settings*. In other words, this resolution identifies CIL as the only wheelchair provider currently eligible to participate in the Government of Georgia wheelchair tender process. This resolution has eliminated the small business wheelchair providers that provided cheap Chinese and Turkish wheelchairs and no service whatsoever from winning any of the State vouchers.

2010: When the State voucher program was first introduced, there were 400 vouchers and all of them serviced by CIL.

2011: Of 650 vouchers, approximately 450 were serviced by CIL.

2012: Of 600 vouchers, approximately 400 were serviced by CIL.

2013: Of 570 vouchers, 450 were serviced by CIL.

2014: There are 350 vouchers for manual wheelchairs and 50 vouchers for power wheelchairs that CIL is working to capture.

Introduction of a New Product: Electric RoughRider™

In 2013, CIL began producing electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs using a new RoughRider™ wheelchair model created in Georgia with greatly reduced armrests. This new model makes it much easier to transfer in and out of the wheelchair by quadriplegics, women with disabilities and others with limited physical strength. In addition, the relatively inexpensive electric wheelchair will afford many Georgians with significant disabilities an opportunity for independence. The Georgian government has agreed to purchase these wheelchairs for qualified individuals including a complete service package.

Wheelchair Provision and Screening Training for Social Workers

CIL has adopted a long-term strategy to expand the availability of wheelchair provision services throughout Georgia and to be able to collect correct information about wheelchair users (their wheelchair needs, measurements, etc.) by training and utilizing specially trained Social Workers in cities and regions. Social Workers have been employed by the Ministry of Health and stationed throughout Georgian rural and urban neighborhoods. They work on the front lines of families with social needs throughout Georgian society and often come to know who has physical disabilities in a family and who needs a wheelchair. CIL will continue conducting training on wheelchair provision screening for Social Workers in different regions and after several trainings, will identify those Social Workers most capable and willing to undergo specialized training in WHO Basic wheelchair provision service.

Wheelchair User Manuals

Wheelchair user manuals started being printed from the day CIL started producing wheelchairs. ***RoughRider™ Wheelchairs User Manuals (3000 copies) were printed and Electric Wheelchair User Manuals (150 copies) were printed and distributed in 2014.*** CIL also prepared and printed two other kinds of informational brochures at different times: **(1) *General Wheelchair Guide describing the procedures under the State voucher program*** for receiving a wheelchair in Georgia; offering different subsidy mechanisms; describing available wheelchairs; contact information; and approximate timeframe were **printed and distributed in 2012 (200 copies); (2) Explanations about the *WHO Guidelines* were printed and distributed in 2013 (150 copies).**

Original Proposal Objective 2: To establish a mobility, self-care, independent living and community accessibility advocacy skill training system for men and women who use wheelchairs in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi.

5 Georgians in wheelchairs (3 men and 2 women) have been trained by WID consultant and international AR expert Tomasz Tasiemski, PhD to be able to train other wheelchair users in wheelchair mobility skills (basic and advanced); activities of daily living; wheelchair sports competitions; weight training; wheelchair outing; lectures on wheelchair adjustment, post-SCI medical complications, prevention of pressure sores, and about concerns regarding SCI sexuality and fertility. The Gori and Zugdidi DPOs can now also provide 1-day wheelchair mobility, maintenance and repair and self-care survival skills workshops to reach a greater number of local wheelchair users in their cities and regions.

Each of the wheelchair mobility skills camps was very well received by all of the participants. All 70 participants came away with valuable lessons and increased skills, regardless of the level at which they began. Some camp participants had not left their homes for years due to both a lack of wheelchair mobility skills as well as psychological barriers and fear of being judged by society. By the end of the camp, these individuals had obviously overcome their most fearful psychological barriers, became motivated to leave their homes and desired to become more socially integrated. All participants made commitments to continue living active lives going forward. Participants, their families and friends found that the often profound changes resulting from this experience should be made more widely available and are critically important to encourage isolated persons with mobility disabilities to become integrated into their communities and have social lives.

Lasha Lomidze (a veteran from the 2008 August war between Georgia and Russia and a wheelchair user from the Sachkhere, Imereti Region), after participating in a CIL-led mobility skills camp, was introduced to the Georgian Paralympic Committee as a promising power-lifter and is now undergoing a training course to prepare for local and international disability sports competitions.

Extension Proposal Objective 2: To fully implement plans to institutionalize the training system of Georgian OTs as postural support seating specialists and to sustain the NDC provision of postural support seating for children in wheelchairs.

NDC provided postural support services according to WHO guidelines mostly for children attending its rehabilitation services and for adults and children needing intermediate or advanced level services referred to them from project partners. These intermediate and advanced services were provided for recipients of CIL RoughRider™ wheelchairs and to wheelchair users with their own wheelchairs acquired outside the project. Sometimes postural support services not linked to a wheelchair were provided, such as stationary chairs for children too young to use a wheelchair, but in need of postural support in the home. Often WHO Intermediate or Advanced postural support services required more than one assessment and fitting.

NDC now has an ongoing clinic for Occupational Therapists (OT) to provide postural support services and equipment, primarily static seating, paid for by the State budget and by families who have the money to pay for the services. **In support of NDC's ongoing clinic, the project also provided:**

- 1. Expert training to 34 professional OTs and OT students in WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services;**
- 2. Institutionalized WHO Basic and Intermediate training within the occupational therapy training course at Georgia State University;**
- 3. Over four years, provided 93 RoughRider™ wheelchairs for low-income adults and children who needed a wheelchair replacement; and**
- 4. Over four years, provided postural support services for 260 adults and children.**

Of the 34 professional OT and OT students, 22 have been trained and certified to provide only WHO Basic services and 12 have been trained and certified to provide WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced services. This group of trained OT professionals also includes 2 internationally certified Master Trainers. One of the OT Master Trainers was invited to attend a regional WHO course on the provision of Intermediate level training in Albania. Their participation at this training event in Albania has helped equip the Georgian OT Master Trainers with experience on how to use the WHO Intermediate training package (the new global standard) within their OT courses at the Georgian State University.

Original Proposal Objective 3: To establish business and advocacy networks between disability communities in Georgia by implementing advocacy, public education, and community accessibility barrier removal activities for persons with mobility impairments and wheelchair users in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi.

Extension Proposal Objective 3: To remove access barriers at important religious, historical and natural sites.

Momentum collectively generated by the advocacy and public education activities conducted by this project led to new DPOs being formed that focused on barrier removal, including the *Movement for an Accessible Environment*, as well as a second USAID-funded project focused on building the advocacy capacity of PWD and building the capacity of regional DPOs. These joint activities raised the profile of disability awareness in Georgia, even gaining the attention and support of the Prime Minister and the declaration of 2013 as the Year of Disability in Georgia. Building on the experience gained by working on this project, at the time of this report, 2 of the advocacy team leaders are running for election to the city councils in Tbilisi and Zugdidi.

Although the actual number of barriers removed was smaller than planned, **the project targeted high profile institutions such as banks and government offices, election voting sites and the Georgian Orthodox Church, which in turn have made independent and ongoing efforts to increase accessibility at sites under their control.** The project worked to increase participation of persons with disabilities in elections by providing foldable metal ramps for key voting sites (constructed by the CIL wheelchair production shop) and by using their accessible van and portable metal ramp to help transport wheelchair users to travel to their election stations on Election Day.

The CIL advocacy team also consulted on **making key Tbilisi tourist destinations accessible for wheelchair users including the National Cathedral; the Finicular tramway station to Mtatsminda Park (CIL has built a ramp at the lower station that allows wheelchair users to enter the tram and also installed a platform lift on the upper station); the renovation of Old Tbilisi neighborhood; the main street of Rusateveli Ave. (construction almost finished); and the Georgian National Museum.** In addition, CIL is currently working with Tbilisi City Hall to adapt the cable car station that takes people up to Narikala Castle in Old Tbilisi.

Public education and mobilization efforts also helped lead to new, significant local and national disability policies including:

1. Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for Persons with Disabilities: In December 2013, the Government of Georgia approved the “Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for Persons with Disabilities,” according to which, all Government buildings must be made accessible for persons with disabilities.

2. Technical Regulations and Standards for Ensuring Architectural and Environmental Accessibility for Persons with Disabilities: Commonly referred to as the “Law on Accessibility”, this legislation is a Prime Ministerial decree signed to law on January 6, 2014. It requires all public and private buildings providing services to the public to make those services accessible to persons with disabilities, including wheelchair users, within a grace period of 5 years.

3. Ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: The UN Convention was ratified on December 27, 2013 and came into force on April 12, 2014. It includes 50 articles setting out provisions for different issues including equality and non-discrimination of persons with disabilities, women with disabilities, children with disabilities, awareness-raising, accessibility, risk and emergency situations, legal rights, security, independent living, mobility, privacy, education, health, employment, rehabilitation, participation in political and public life, etc.

4. Adoption of the law, Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination: On May 2, 2014, this anti-discrimination law was adopted unanimously by the Georgian Parliament and went into force on May 7, 2014. It prohibits discrimination on the basis of a person’s gender, age, religion, language, sexual orientation, gender identity, political affiliation or ethnicity. It also prohibits discrimination against those with a disability. Additional anti-discrimination legislation

specifically protecting the rights of persons with disabilities is currently being drafted by a national expert group and must be finalized by the end of June 2014.

5. Adoption of Disabled Parking in Tbilisi: The Tbilisi Municipality and C.T. PARK have allocated special parking spaces for persons with disabilities. Disability advocates complain that, while the parking spaces have been allocated and the identification mechanism developed by City Hall, it is not effective because only those people with disabilities who own a vehicle can obtain the special permission to park in these parking spaces. Parents who drive their children or those persons with disabilities who do not own the vehicle cannot get a permit.

6. Government of Georgia Resolution No. 216 on Approving the 2013 State Program on Social Rehabilitation and Childcare: On August 23, 2013, the Government of Georgia amended its wheelchair provision resolution, according to which the government commits to procuring only wheelchairs produced in Georgia to support the local wheelchair production and the employment of persons with disabilities. It requires that Georgia adhere to the international standards for wheelchair production and service outlined in the World Health Organization's *Guidelines on the Provision of Manual Wheelchairs in Less Resourced Settings*. This resolution leaves CIL as the only wheelchair provider currently eligible to participate in the tender process until other competing wheelchair producers meet the criteria as currently established in Georgia. This eliminates participation of wheelchair providers that provide cheap Chinese and Turkish wheelchairs and no service whatsoever, from participating in the State voucher program.

d. Follow up and sustainability of program

CIL Wheelchair Production Shop Control

WID and its partners set up a wheelchair production and repair facility in Tbilisi and small, networked wheelchair sales, distribution and repair businesses in Gori and Zugdidi. WID and our 4 Georgian NGO partners established the Georgian Wheelchair Production Network, which is supported by a wheelchair production and repair business in Tbilisi, which produces and sells an adult and child model of the manual RoughRider™ indoor-outdoor wheelchair; an electric version of the RoughRider™ wheelchair; pressure relief wheelchair cushions; metal folding ramps; car hand controls and other assistive mobility products for Georgian wheelchair users; and small wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi.

At the close of this project, WID is passing control of the wheelchair production facility to CIL, the principal implementing partner that continues to operate and manage the wheelchair production business; wheelchair provision services; making and providing comfort and pressure relieving cushions; and a public showroom for selling its wheelchairs and other assistive devices.

WID and CIL have turned over control of the 2 regional wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi to the Gori Disabled Club and Association DEA respectively.

Sustainability of CIL Wheelchair Production Business

In 2014, CIL delivered 273 RoughRider™ wheelchairs and 35 electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs to the US Embassy, which is working with the Healthcare Ministry and the Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons, in order to identify adults and children in need of wheelchairs.

Today, CIL also continues to provide wheelchairs to the Government of Georgia within the 2014 voucher program. Starting from June 2014, the number of wheelchairs to be purchased by the Government in 2014 is 350 manual wheelchairs at 300 GEL (\$170 according to the current exchange rate) and 50 electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs at 3,480 GEL (\$1,970). CIL is continuously negotiating with the Ministry of Healthcare in order to increase the voucher price for manual wheelchairs and is expecting this change in 2015.

For the clients who received the electric RoughRider™ wheelchairs, CIL and NDC have conducted an individual assessment of each client and provided individualized fitting and adjustment of the wheelchairs when the chairs were delivered to their owners. The individualized assessments and fitting took place in Tbilisi, Gori, Kutaisi, Qobuleti and Batumi and whenever necessary, also occurred in the client's home.

In 2014, CIL has also completed an order of 325 RoughRider™ wheelchairs for LDS Charities/Georgia, at \$248 each. Although not finally confirmed yet, there are new orders from LDS Charities/Armenia for 15 RoughRider™ wheelchairs at \$248 each and from UNHCR/Georgia for 60 the RoughRider™ wheelchairs at \$250 each.

In May 2014, the President of CIL, Mr. Dzneladze, traveled to China in order to meet with wheelchair factories and suppliers and identified several sourcing options for greatly reducing current CIL wheelchair production costs. In addition, Mr. Dzneladze identified institutional and adjustable wheelchairs at a higher quality and lower cost than previously purchased from Turkey.

CIL is continuing to employ, using the income from the wheelchair production business, the wheelchair factory managers and shop floor workers, which include five wheelchair users. Mr. Dzneladze has stated that, **while employing the wheelchair production shop workers, providing wheelchair provision and repair services and buying pressure relieving cushions, he believes that based on the 2014 planned wheelchair purchases, by December 2014, CIL is expecting \$41,000 in profit out of which 15% will be paid to the State budget as CIL profit tax and the remaining profit used as working capital to sustain production.**

Also, according to ongoing negotiations with LDS Charities/Georgia, in 2015, LDS Charities will place an order for more than 600 RoughRider™ wheelchairs. **Therefore, WID can state with full confidence that the sustainability of CIL wheelchair production has been achieved throughout 2015, thanks to the hard work of CIL and many others involved in this project.**

Humanitarian and International NGOs donations of wheelchairs to Georgia are usually purchased from CIL and from China. Even though the yearly combined number of CIL wheelchair sales is now sufficient to sustain the economic viability of the wheelchair production business, the CIL wheelchair production business must continue to lower its costs and grow its list of buyers, production volume and model diversity in order to continue being economically sustainable under Georgian market constraints.

Wheelchair Mobility Skills Training and Camps

The CIL wheelchair mobility skills training team, consisting of 5 Georgian trainers in wheelchairs (3 men and 2 women), have successfully demonstrated their capacity to continue to

provide training in wheelchair mobility skills (basic and advanced); activities of daily living; wheelchair sports competitions; weight training; wheelchair outing; lectures on wheelchair adjustment, post-SCI medical complications, prevention of pressure sores, sexuality and fertility at twice a year, five-day wheelchair mobility and self-care skills training camps for groups of 20 men and women who use wheelchairs. The DPO advocacy team members in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi also have successfully demonstrated their capacity to provide training in wheelchair mobility skills at 1-day wheelchair mobility, maintenance and repair and self-care survival skills events. The DPOs in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi are capable of continuing to provide the 1-day wheelchair mobility, maintenance and repair and self-care survival skills events.

Due to the high cost, \$15,000 - \$20,000, associated with implementing a 5-day active rehabilitation and mobility skills camp for only 20 wheelchair users at a time, WID and CIL believe that these camps are not financially sustainable and will not continue after project funding ceases since it is not realistic to expect the Georgian government to pay the high costs associated with organizing and implementing active rehabilitation and mobility skills camps for the many hundreds of wheelchair users who would benefit from participation. CIL has requested new funding from the Polish government and from a Georgian foundation in order to continue providing the urgently needed wheelchair mobility skills camps.

WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced Equipment and Services

Throughout the course of the project after receiving international expert training, NDC has provided WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced equipment and services only with project funds. The Georgian government has so far refused to include the cost of WHO intermediate Services provision in its state budget calculation for what it is willing to pay for under the State voucher program, other than for power wheelchairs, where Intermediate service provision is included in the electric wheelchair voucher cost. This reflects a mentality prevalent in Georgian society and within the Ministry of Labour, Health and Social Affairs that wheelchairs are commercial objects as opposed to the concept reflected in the WHO Guidelines, which includes the production and provision of wheelchairs and other assistive equipment within the framework of “wheelchair provision services.”

NDC will continue to provide an ongoing clinic for OTs to provide WHO Basic, Intermediate and Advanced wheelchair provision services paid for by families who have the money to pay for the services. Adults and children clients who cannot afford to pay for the services will have to wait until the Ministry of Health voucher system has agreed to subsidize these services.

The Georgia State University will continue to provide the WHO Wheelchair Service Training Package, Basic and Intermediate levels, in its OT training course. The Georgia State University training program will continue to graduate new OTs who will have the knowledge and skills to provide these services to their future clients.

By the end of the project, 34 professional OTs and OT students had received the WHO Wheelchair Service Training Package, and had been certified to provide Basic, Intermediate or Advanced wheelchair provision services. This group of trained professionals also included 2 Master Trainers. One of the OT Master Trainers was invited to attend a regional WHO course on the provision of Intermediate level training in Albania. Their participation at the training event in

Albania has helped equip the Georgian OT Master Trainers with experience on how to use the WHO Intermediate training package (the new global standard) within their OT courses at the Georgian State University.

Sustainability of Postural Support Services

It is difficult to determine the real cost of providing postural support services and equipment because the services vary widely according to the needs of an individual client. None the less, NDC has produced a cost analysis for its postural support services, calculated on the level of need of each individual served, including equipment cost, fitting and follow-up. The equipment cost, in addition to the cost of a RoughRider™ wheelchair (*if the client's wheelchair is not in good condition*) is a pressure relief cushion plus the cost of providing postural support equipment components. By definition, Basic service include assessment but does not require modifications for postural support. NDC estimates that that **cost per person served at the Basic level of service is GEL 149/person (\$84 USD)**. Intermediate services require some modifications and provision of postural support equipment components. NDC's estimated **cost per person served at the Intermediate level of service is GEL 539.80 (\$305 USD)**. Advanced service requires both additional time and the provision of postural support equipment components adapted specifically to the individual's needs and costs. NDC's estimated **cost per person served at the Advanced level is GEL 743 (\$420 USD) per person**. For NDC, the sustainability problem remains in that at the time of this report, there is no Government Voucher funding to support any level of this service.

Both CIL and NDC have been advocating for the Georgian government to include funds for WHO Intermediate Services provision within the State voucher program. In March 2013, Mr. Kakushadze was informed that the WHO assessments and postural support services had been included in the *State Disability Action Plan 2013-2016*. Unfortunately, money to pay for these services was not included in the State budget funding for 2014.

In May 2014, Mr. Kakushadze of NDC met with Social Affairs Agency officials at the Ministry of Labor, Health and Social Affairs, who expressed hope that NDC would receive funding from the Ministry to provide the full range of Postural Support Services to 10 people per month from the State budget in 2014-2015. This would more than cover the costs that the project expended on these services over a similar period of time. However, there has been no decision made as of this report.

Community Accessibility, Public Education and Advocacy Initiatives

The DPOs in Tbilisi, Gori and Zugdidi have the skills, knowledge and capacity to continue to implement community accessibility, public education and advocacy activities using local, state and international resources. The project hopes that advocacy activities started by this project will be continued due to the implementation of the new disability laws and policies passed by the Georgian government. By enlisting the support and collaboration of institutions like the Church and banks, the project hopes that they, too, will continue their efforts to make their buildings and services accessible to persons with disabilities. CIL has also secured new projects and resources to continue to advocate for barrier-free environments, rights and inclusion of Georgians with disabilities.

e. Summary of Indicators

Statistical information was provided from all Georgian DPO and NGO partners every quarter during the 20 quarters of the project. Quarter 21 was only two months and after project activities had ended in Georgia. Program activities, accomplishments and statistical information from the regional DPOs were provided to CIL, who then combined the regional statistical information with CIL’s own statistical information and forwarded that to WID. NDC submitted their statistical information to WID, who then reviewed their statistics and, if necessary, asked for any additional information, such as male or female or age. WID’s project director also reviewed the statistical information provided by CIL and, if necessary, asked for additional statistical information if it had not been provided, such as male or female or age.

In the first four years of the project, WID’s project director also received program statistical information from WWI every quarter, and for the last four years of the project, WID received any training program statistical information every quarter from their consultant, Jamie Noon. WID’s project director submitted the combined project statistical indicators form every quarter to World Learning, who then reviewed the combined project statistical indicators form and, if necessary, asked for corrections to be made.

Indicators Tab #1 Number of people receiving wheelchairs, tricycles, or related services through the project:

NDC provided postural support services to 260 children and adults, of which 155 were males and 105 were females. NDC provided postural support services and a new RoughRider™ wheelchair for 93 children and adults (52 males, 41 females). NDC provided postural support services for 167 children and adults using their current wheelchairs and for 24 children using a static seating chair (listed in Other). NDC provided postural support services for almost all of the 69 children and adults who received an electric RoughRider™ wheelchair (included in previously mentioned 260 persons served by NDC).

CIL provided 1,256 RoughRider™ wheelchairs (without provision services) to males and 672 to females.

The wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi were not operational until the 4th year of the project and they provided wheelchair repair services for 107 adults and children, of which 64 were males and 43 were female.

	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>	<i>Total</i>
People receiving postural support services from NDC	103	64	167
People receiving CIL RoughRider™ wheelchairs (with provision services)	52	42	93
People receiving CIL	1,256	672	1,928

RoughRider™ wheelchairs (without provision services)			
People receiving wheelchair repair services	64	43	107
Other (Static Seating Chairs)	12	12	24
Total Served	1,487	832	2,319

Indicators Tab #2 Number of information sharing or social protection activities provided through the project and people/organizations benefiting from these activities:

During the five-year project, CIL and its regional partners in Gori and Zugdidi conducted 264 project activities, which approximately benefited 2,998 persons, of which 1,529 were males and 1,464 were females.

During the five-year project, approximately 325 organizations benefited from activities by the project partners, of which 6 were faith-based organizations, 88 were government organizations, 105 were disability organizations, 67 were NGOs, 3 were community-based organizations and 56 were some other type of organization.

Indicators Tab #3 Number of individuals/organizations benefiting from capacity building (training activities) provided through the project:

During the five-year project, CIL and its regional partners in Gori and Zugdidi conducted 33 capacity building training activities, which benefited approximately 398 persons, of which 121 were men with disabilities, 85 were women with disabilities, 44 were non-disabled men males and 148 were non-disabled women.

During the five-year project, the 33 capacity building training activities, conducted by CIL and its regional partners in Gori and Zugdidi, benefited 1 government, 6 disability organizations, and 8 NGOs.

Indicators Tab #3a. Number of organizations benefiting from capacity building activities (provision of equipment, materials, funds) provided through the project:

During the five-year project, NDC, CIL and its regional partners in Gori and Zugdidi benefited from capacity building activities (provision of equipment, materials, funds) provided through the project (\$1,083,535). CIL and its 2 regional DPO partners benefited 27 times and NDC benefited 10 times.

Indicators Tab #4 Number of people participating in increased economic self-sufficiency:

During the five-year project, CIL and its regional partners in Gori and Zugdidi helped to increase economic self-sufficiency for 11 male wheelchair users (6 shop workers, 2 mechanics, 3

advocates); 3 female wheelchair users (3 advocates); 3 male non wheelchair users (3 non-disabled shop workers); and 3 female non-wheelchair users (1 non-disabled interpreter/manager and 2 female advocates with mobility impairments (use crutches/wheelchair).

Indicators Tab #5 Cumulative Common Indicators:

In summary, during the five-year project, 5,337 persons were served by the project, of which 3,030 were males and 2,307 were females. During the five-year project, 398 persons were trained, of which 165 were males and 233 were females.

During the five-year project, 377 organizations were strengthened by improving their capacity to provide services for persons with disabilities.

V. Problems Encountered and Solutions

- a. Key problems/challenges faced in management and program

WID Management Problems and Challenges

WWI and SFSU Financial Management Issues

Whirlwind Wheelchair International (WWI) started the project as a sub award partner, under the fiscal management of San Francisco State University (SFSU), with the project responsibility of managing and supervising the WWI sub award for CIL in order to start up the wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop. WWI, through their international consultant, Mr. Afonin, was able to substantially help CIL set up the first wheelchair production shop and successfully train the shop managers and shop floor workers to start up wheelchair production. WWI was also substantially helpful to CIL with implementing quality control procedures and with resolving technical wheelchair production issues.

However, WID encountered repeated program and financial report submission delays and financial report inaccuracies from WWI and SFSU, a few times during the first year of the project and more frequently during the second and third years of the project. WWI legally and financially operated under the fiscal management of the administration of SFSU. Therefore, the administration of San Francisco State University had to approve all financial and international travel decisions made by WWI and SFSU provided the official financial program reports to WID. This created a double layer of administration, which became a significant problem. WWI was constantly being forced to pressure SFSU administration staff to deliver project program and financial reports before rather than after required deadlines; correct SFSU administration and financial mistakes; and to personally intervene with SFSU higher authorities in order to get very basic and simple reporting procedures implemented correctly and on time.

This led to extra work for WID staff and to some delays in WID's meeting of required report deadlines.

WWI Management Problems and Challenges

Delayed Implementation Of Wheelchair Production

April 2010, After WWI's first project year of providing support for the start up the wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop, WWI was not as proactive in providing full responsibility and involvement in the normal month-to-month managing and supervising of CIL's ongoing wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop efforts. However, WWI's contribution to the success of the CIL wheelchair production business and wheelchair production shop was not their only area of responsibility in the project.

Delayed Implementation Of Postural Support Seating Equipment And Services

The original project planned to use an orthotics NGO, the Georgian Foundation for Prosthetics and Orthotics (GEFPOR), as the implementing partner for providing postural support seating equipment and services. However, during the first project implementation trip to Georgia, the WID project director and Jamie Noon held a preliminary planning discussion with the GEFPOR

Director and senior staff and left that meeting with serious reservations about the appropriateness of trying to start a completely new type of rehabilitation technology and disability service within the GEFPOR orthotic facilities and medically focused organizational mission. The WID project director realized that he was just beginning to implement the project activities in Georgia and one of the major implementing partners was no longer considered appropriate and that a new organizational implementing partner needed to be identified immediately.

WID had also expected expert assistance from WWI on setting up and managing the postural support services component of the project, but it quickly became evident that WWI expected Jamie Noon, WID's international expert consultant, to provide all expert assistance on implementing this project program. This also contributed to a delayed start up of this program component and added to the implementation workload of WID project staff.

Delayed Implementation of the Regional Wheelchair Sales And Repair Shops

After the first year and a half of the project and after wheelchair production had started, WID had expected expert assistance from WWI on setting up and managing the regional wheelchair sales and repair shops. WWI participated in the project conversations with WID and CIL on setting up the regional wheelchair sales and repair shops and later WWI participated in the WID/CIL/WWI project conversations analyzing and evaluating the obstacles confronting setting up these regional shops but, WWI was not proactive in managing the development and operation of these CIL regional shops. This lack of assisting in program implementation by WWI also added to the implementation workload of WID staff.

WID Program Implementation Problems and Challenges

USAID Reduction of WID's Original 3-Year Project Budget in 2009

During WID's pre-award negotiations, USAID reduced the submitted project budget from the requested \$2 million down to \$1.4 million. By June 2010, After 5 quarters of trying to implement the project, WID was beginning to experience negative management and program repercussions from USAID's severe reduction (\$600K) to the funding originally requested by the project partners. This reduction in project funding was accomplished by reducing WID, WWI and CIL staff FTE time, the number of trips to Georgia by the American partners and the amount of money available for CIL to implement and manage many of the project activities. All project partners sacrificed, when reducing their original planned budgets, in order to make the project successful on a smaller budget. However, the over 25% reduction in funding for the project led to some negative consequences that manifested over several years in WID project staff overload, reduced CIL administration and implementation staff in Georgia and no room for error or dealing with unexpected problems while implementing project activities. WID remained concerned that these negative issues would continue to manifest in the project, since some of the greatest funding reductions were taken from the second and third year budgets for the project.

Submission of Quarterly Program and Financial Reports by Deadlines

During the first year of the project, the Georgian disability partners were not consistent in their reporting of the implementation of activities according to their agreed-upon work plan; their reporting of program activity statistics on the required indicator forms; and the documentation of their expenses on the required financial forms. All of the Georgian disability NGO partners did

not have prior experience with USAID reporting forms or with an organizational work culture of paper documentation when implementing activities. All of these project partner report irregularities contributed to the additional work and frustration for CIL and WID in preparing and submitting their quarterly program and financial reports on time and with dependable information.

Partners' Problems with World Learning/USAID Statistical and Financial Forms

By January 2012, WID had received several notices from WL that indicated errors were being made when filling out the indicator forms. WID made the corrections requested and resubmitted the indicator forms to WL. WID had also notified CIL about the previous indicator forms with errors, which they had submitted to WID. There was an attempt made by the WID project director to train the CIL project administrator on the correct way to fill out the indicator forms. However, the WL/USAID statistical indicator forms were very complicated, somewhat confusing as to the cumulative addition process and open to subjective interpretation as to how to correctly identify quantitative numbers.

Minimal And Unchanging Government Budget For Addressing Disability Issues

During the first three years of the project, the Government of Georgia appropriated very low national budgets for addressing the needs of adults and children with disabilities. In addition, almost all Government regulations and laws pertaining to the needs of persons with disabilities were not being enforced. The personal, social, medical and economic inclusion needs of adults and children using wheelchairs were addressed minimally by the government politicians and the low political priority of PWD was reflected in the low amount of funds allocated, which was yearly appropriated for the national disability budget. The minimal Government disability budget caused our project partners and CIL two problems: 1) the low number of wheelchair vouchers available in the first several years of the project; and (2) the low amount of money paid for purchasing wheelchairs by the national voucher system. Both of these problems created an unsustainable business model and strongly threatened the present and future economic sustainability of the CIL wheelchair production business.

Lack of Enforcement of the Government Law on Architectural Accessibility

Regrettably, there is an almost universal lack of enforcement of existing Georgian law, which requires all new buildings to be constructed with accessibility for persons with mobility problems. Everywhere throughout Georgia almost every building has steps, which is a direct legacy of previous Soviet building construction practice. The general lack of physical infrastructure accessibility and the lack of public transportation accessibility are two of the main reasons why persons who use wheelchairs are isolated in their homes and generally invisible and excluded in Georgian society.

The lack of enforcement about creating accessibility when constructing new buildings is especially frustrating when existing street curb ramps are demolished when modernizing streets during city renovations. In addition, since 2008 the Georgian government has been very active in promoting the modernization of city infrastructure throughout Georgia and hundreds of buildings have been constructed without any accessibility for persons using wheelchairs.

In September 2011, the WID project director discussed with the USAID Mission staff in Georgia the USAID regulations on mandating architectural accessibility when constructing new buildings and facilities and inquired about whom at USAID is responsible for monitoring Georgian government compliance when USAID funds are involved in infrastructure building or renovation. Mr. Curtis gave details of his recent observations while visiting the World Heritage town of Svaneti. The Georgian government has determined that Svaneti would become a tourist destination for skiers in the winter and also for many tourists during the summer and was completely rebuilding the downtown business and hotel area. All of the newly constructed buildings had multiple steps at the entrances. The USAID Health representative pointed out the insufficient number of USAID staff to adequately provide monitoring for Georgian government compliance on mandated architectural accessibility standards.

Introduction of a Government National Voucher System

In 2011, the Ministry of Health introduced a national voucher system for providing eligible medical services and medical equipment, which could be used by persons living below the poverty line who needed a wheelchair. Under the new national voucher system, wheelchairs were partially subsidized when purchased and provided to adults and children with mobility problems. This national voucher program was a first time experience in Georgia, almost everyone did not understand the rules or procedures in obtaining or utilizing a voucher, and often the voucher clients needed assistance and prompting at each step.

The national voucher system had a policy of supporting a free market choice for all persons who needed wheelchairs, and the Georgian authorities responsible for determining the Government tender requirements were not willing to provide a sole-source contract to CIL for purchasing only RoughRider™ wheelchairs. In order to successfully compete and continue to win the government tender for wheelchair purchases, CIL also needed to provide for the voucher clients, institutional style and adjustable adult wheelchairs, which CIL could purchase from Turkey.

In 2011, CIL had just completed setting up the wheelchair production shop and was deeply motivated to secure their first sale of 100 wheelchairs to the government, CIL therefore agreed to participate in this new national voucher system without fully comprehending what all was required in completing the Government paperwork and the delivery of the wheelchair to the voucher clients. As it turned out, a great deal of additional CIL staff time and transportation expense was necessary to assist the clients by completing their voucher paperwork and sometimes just to get on the official wheelchair waiting list; helping to document their identity credentials and doctor prescription; conducting a wheelchair assessment by telephone for remote clients; and delivering the wheelchair to the client, which sometimes included delivery to their doorstep in distant towns or rural areas.

The government tender regulations stated that the wheelchair provider businesses (who had competed and won the government tender approval) were responsible for completing the government paperwork and for delivering the wheelchairs to the voucher client and both actions were required to be completed within the low cost per wheelchair provided by the national voucher system. All of these national voucher implementation regulations combined with the government purchasing wheelchairs at a low set price, created an unsustainable business model and strongly threatened the economic viability of the CIL wheelchair production business.

National Voucher System Wheelchair Price is Too Low

From 2011 through 2013, the amount paid by the national voucher program to sell wheelchairs to the government did not even cover the complete cost of fabricating the CIL RoughRider™ wheelchair and did not pay for CIL's additional work of completing the government paperwork, providing an individual wheelchair assessment or for delivering the wheelchair to the client, sometimes in distant parts of the country. During 2013, CIL conducted intense discussions over several months with the Deputy Minister of Health, in order to increase the amount of money paid by the government voucher program for CIL's wheelchairs and their provision and follow-up support services. The Deputy Minister of Health, who was appointed by the previous government, which lost the election in October 2012, said that he did not have the authority to increase the voucher price. The Prime Minister's government is directly responsible for managing the prices covered by the government wheelchair tenders and the voucher system.

In June 13 2013, CIL decided that the low payment amount provided by the Ministry of Health voucher program for purchasing and providing wheelchairs would not economically support the continuation of the CIL wheelchair production business, and therefore, CIL decided to publicly announce that they were stopping production of wheelchairs for sale to the government and to publicly announce that CIL would boycott participation in the 2013 government wheelchair voucher program. This extreme action by CIL was a high-stakes gamble for their current and future economic profitability, which greatly worried WID since it threatened the success of the central project component.

Negative Government Wheelchair Purchasing Tender Policies

During each of the first three years of the project, CIL participated in the Government tender competition process for wheelchair purchases, which was designed by the government to be competitive and nondiscriminatory towards any wheelchair provider that wanted to sell wheelchairs to the government. However, the Government price paid for wheelchairs by was set very low and the nondiscriminatory procedures of the tender bidding process resulted in CIL competing with small wheelchair provider businesses who imported cheap wheelchairs from Turkey or China and sold them to the government with no guarantees or wheelchair provision services. The small wheelchair provider businesses were still able to make a profit from selling cheap wheelchairs to the government, even at a low Government tender price, while CIL was forced to sell its RoughRider™ wheelchair at a significant loss and still include voucher client marketing phone calls, filling out Government paperwork for each client and trying to provide wheelchair assessment and provision services.

The Completion of the First CIL Wheelchair Production Shop

By March 2010, the completion of the physical setup of the wheelchair production shop did not happen as originally scheduled due to the late calendar awarding of the USAID project contract and the late project start up in 2009. Fully equipping the shop with machinery and setting up the workstations also took longer due to WWI's consultant, Mr. Afonin, creative construction of some shop equipment and workstations, in order to reduce shop startup costs and save money. The scheduled WWI training of the wheelchair production shop managers and workers was also delayed, and when the training was actually conducted, the WWI training team was not able to complete all of their planned skill-based training because the equipment and workstations for the

wheelchair production line was not completely set up. WWI's consultant, Mr. Afonin, was asked to finish the planned skill-based training over the following months.

After April 2010, WWI staff in San Francisco was less involved in problem-solving communications with the CIL project coordinator or the wheelchair production shop managers as the Georgians encountered problems in the shop production set up and in their sourcing for wheelchair production materials. WWI was primarily relying on Mr. Afonin's technical expertise and on-site consultation to provide supervision and to solve any production problems. This technical assistance strategy worked during the months when Mr. Afonin was staying in Georgia but not very well during the months of time when he was not in Georgia.

Locally Constructing Pressure Relieving Cushions

The project helped 2 different disability businesses in two different cities to manufacture a comfort cushion and a pressure relief cushion. The pressure relief cushion cost approximately \$25, which, unfortunately, was a lot of money to add to the cost of a wheelchair. Therefore, in the first three project years, because of the below cost Government voucher price for wheelchairs, CIL did not provide a Georgian made pressure relief cushion for those who needed one with their wheelchair unless the client personally paid extra for it. This CIL policy did not support WHO wheelchair provision guidelines and created concerns and criticism from USAID when it was reported by WID. This CIL policy did not apply to wheelchairs bought by LDS, which was willing to pay extra for the pressure relief cushions.

Wheelchair Provision Includes A Pressure Relief Cushion When Needed

During the first three years of the project, CIL was struggling to financially survive as a wheelchair production business because the government voucher system, which was the primary purchaser of CIL wheelchairs, had set a low price for wheelchairs, that did not cover the total costs of CIL to manufacture a RoughRider™ wheelchair or to purchase a Georgian made pressure relief cushion or to conduct a face-to-face wheelchair assessment or to complete the voucher system paperwork or to deliver the wheelchair to the client.

Need for Wheelchair Provision Screening Workshop with Social Workers

WHO wheelchair provision guidelines recommend a face-to-face interview with an individual who has been trained and certified according to WHO Basic guidelines. Regrettably, WID and CIL realized that the available project staff, which was trained to provide Basic assessment for wheelchair provision, was too few in number to be able to appropriately meet the wheelchair provision needs of Georgia. Trained CIL staff were completely overwhelmed trying to provide appropriate Basic assessments for the hundreds of wheelchair users living all over Georgia who were receiving new RoughRider™ wheelchairs, which resulted in a high percentage of voucher clients receiving instead, questions over the telephone about what type of wheelchair did they need and instructions about how to conduct accurate measurements of their bodies for an appropriate wheelchair.

CIL decided that they needed to develop a long-term strategy to improve wheelchair provision services throughout Georgia by dramatically increasing the number of WHO Basic qualified individuals who were able to collect correct information about wheelchair users (their needs, measurements, etc.) from across the country. CIL identified the new profession of Social

Workers, which have been employed by the Ministry of Health and stationed throughout Georgian rural and urban neighborhoods, as an ideal choice for quickly expanding the numbers of professionals who could be trained to provide Basic wheelchair assessment. The Social Workers worked everywhere throughout Georgia on the front lines of families with social needs and often came to know who has physical mobility disabilities in a family and who needs a wheelchair. However, the social workers had never received any direct training about disability awareness; the different wheelchair needs of wheelchair users; the availability of different types of wheelchairs in Georgia; typical health problems of some wheelchair users such as pressure sores; and how to conduct a WHO Basic wheelchair assessment.

Wheelchair Mobility And Independent Living Skills Training Camps

In 2012, CIL was unable to conduct a 5-Day wheelchair mobility skills training and active rehabilitation camp for wheelchair users due to the fact that an Azerbaijani petroleum company had leased for 1 year, the accessible motel where CIL had previously held the 5-day wheelchair mobility skills training and active rehabilitation camps. After many inspections at hotels and other facilities throughout the country, CIL could not identify an appropriate site for conducting a training camp that could provide both accessible accommodation for about 25 wheelchair users as well as suitable indoor/outdoor facilities for wheelchair mobility skills training and sports activities. CIL staff exhaustively searched for this kind of accessible facility all over Georgia and could not identify a single site, which provided affordable and accessible housing and accessible wheelchair training space.

At the same time, the project partners had become concerned about the high costs associated with implementing the 5-Day wheelchair mobility skills training camps for about 20 wheelchair users per camp. These high costs were paid for only by the project budget. WID and CIL did not believe it was realistic to expect the Georgian government to agree to pay for organizing and implementing active rehabilitation and wheelchair mobility skills training camps after project funding ended. Therefore, CIL agreed to continue their efforts to educate the new government authorities about the usefulness and the need for these active rehabilitation and wheelchair mobility skills training camps and to request partial or full government funding to support the implementation of future camps.

By March 2011, WID and CIL needed to increase the number of wheelchair users who received wheelchair mobility skills training in order to meet the project targets. However, WID and CIL were in agreement that the project budget was not able to afford the high cost of providing multiple events consisting of weeklong training camps for 20 wheelchair users in order to quickly increase the project numbers. Therefore, the total number of wheelchair users who had received wheelchair mobility skills training was much lower than what was projected at the beginning of the project.

Implementing Postural Support Seating Equipment and Services Program

WID did not any have prior experience with creating and implementing a postural support seating equipment and services program. Therefore, the original three-year project budget was not well-developed and funded in order to fully support the creation and implementation of this component of the project.

In addition, because the original implementing partner, GEFPOR, turned out to not be an appropriate implementing organization, WID had to quickly develop a new organizational and management relationship with a previously unknown sub award partner located in Tbilisi, The Treatment and Educational Center of Child Neurology and Neuro Rehabilitation (CCNNR), in order to implement the postural support seating equipment and services component of the project. This effort required additional time and implementation attention from WID project staff in order to develop a work plan and budget that could adequately implement this project component.

No Public Understanding of Postural Support Seating Equipment and Services

By June 2010, the implementation of this major project activity by CCNNR and the OTs was proceeding quite well and the only difficulty was a more substantial and comprehensive realization by WID and Mr. Noon that Georgians were completely unaware of this technology, its benefits and the project's attempt to introduce postural support seating equipment and services to Georgia. There was a great need for public education activities in order to promote the understanding and demand for postural support seating equipment and services by Georgian families and adults with mobility impairments.

Implementation of Regional Postural Support Sitting Services

The WID project director became concerned about the need to educate families and professionals outside of the capital of Tbilisi about the availability of postural support seating equipment and services. There obviously were families with children and adults living the remote cities and regions of Georgia, who needed access to these life-changing equipment and services. The CCNNR (NDC was still CCNNR at this time) Program Director was very reluctant to utilize public media to announce the availability of postural support seating equipment and services at CCNNR because he did not want to create a long waiting list, which would only increase the frustration of the families waiting to receive services. In addition, the only trained professionals available to provide these services lived and worked at CCNNR in Tbilisi.

Completion of the New Wheelchair Production Shop

CIL's overall wheelchair production numbers, quality control efforts and need for physical expansion were restricted by their first wheelchair production shop, which was located in a very small space. In the first CIL wheelchair production shop, there was not enough space to operate more than one wheelchair production line; they did not have any available space for a ramp to test if the wheelchairs rolled straight; and they needed additional raw materials and finished wheelchairs storage space as their wheelchair sales orders increased.

Implementation of a CIL Wheelchair Products Showroom for the Public

In 2012, USAID and all of the project partners agreed that the CIL wheelchair production business would greatly benefit from having a public showroom containing different models of wheelchairs, various types of seating cushions, examples of postural support seating equipment, folding lightweight metal ramps, and different types of assistive products and, ideally, with the physical space for the public to experiment with different types of wheelchairs and a private space for a person to be measured for a wheelchair. Therefore, this activity was contained in the supplemental funding proposal and was planned to be included in the outcome of renovating and constructing the new, larger CIL wheelchair production shop. However, when the new CIL

wheelchair production shop was finished and when the WID project director visited the renovated and functioning wheelchair production building for the first time, a wheelchair products showroom for the public was not included.

Sustainability of the Wheelchair Production Business

From the beginning of the project, there were always obstacles and unknowns to the profitability and economic sustainability of the CIL wheelchair production business. The quality of the wheelchairs produced was not stabilized until three years into the project. The numbers of wheelchairs purchased by the government voucher program or other buyers were never sufficient because the price paid by the government voucher program was too low and below the cost of production for the business to make a profit. CIL needed to increase the level of wheelchair production, but they did not move into a larger building that would allow greater production until the third year of the project. CIL needed to add different and more profitable wheelchairs for sale, but that did not occur until the fourth year of the project with their introduction of the electric RoughRider™ wheelchair, which had a significant profit margin when sold to the government voucher program. CIL needed to eliminate or greatly reduce business competitors in the government voucher program, but that was not accomplished until just before the project ended. Until project year 5, there was always some level of uncertainty about the future sustainability of the CIL wheelchair production business.

Implementation of Regional Wheelchair Sales and Repair Shops

The implementation of the set-up of the regional wheelchair repair shops was repeatedly delayed throughout the first 3 project years because all of the project partners agreed that there were not enough wheelchairs to support these repair businesses. Therefore, the wheelchair repair training for the mechanics was delayed until the fourth year of the project.

By September 2010, the WID project director conducted several informal conversations with our project partners in Zugdidi, Gori and Tbilisi about our original project activity of developing local wheelchair sales and repair micro-businesses. Everyone is in agreement that the economic reality of most families and a lack of money; the lack of sufficient new and used wheelchairs to economically support a wheelchair repair business; and our greatly reduced project budget, all taken together did not support continuing with this project activity. However, the regional DPOs did not want to give up on their creation of wheelchair repair shops, but they did not have any resources to create them either.

Training in Micro-Business Management for Regional Repair Mechanics

WID had proposed in the original project proposal and in the supplemental funding proposal to provide micro-business management training for the mechanics working in the regional wheelchair repair shops. Unfortunately, the pro bono business training offered by the OSCE that was identified in the original proposal ceased to be an option after the OSCE Mission to Georgia closed. WID was not successful in its efforts to identify a micro-business management training program available for persons living in the regions that was offered for free until very late in the project.

Underperformance of the Community Accessibility Barrier Removal Mini-Projects

The community advocacy teams continue to underperform each quarter in the amount of barrier removal projects that are started and completed. WID had originally budgeted \$500 for each community barrier removal mini-project, which was to be used as a stimulus by the community advocacy teams in order to leverage additional resources to complete the barrier removal mini-project. For some small mini-projects, \$500 was sufficient to negotiate the installation of a simple ramp. For other mini-projects, \$500 was useful for beginning negotiations, but it was not a sufficient amount of money in order to successfully complete the construction of accessibility for a building and additional outside resources to complete the construction were not easily available.

Need for Public Education about Pressure Sores and the Total Lack of Medical Services to Treat Pressure Sores in Georgia

WID and CIL staff organized a meeting in September 2013 on how to develop a public education campaign to address the serious problem of Georgians with life-threatening pressure sores and the lack of general understanding and knowledge in Georgian doctors about how to prevent or heal pressure sores. The discussion in this meeting became focused on providing surgical treatment for closing severe pressure sores in life-threatening cases. There was general agreement to approach the Ministry of Health and request their financial support for bringing an experienced Armenian doctor to Georgia in order to provide immediate surgical treatment to Georgians with severe pressure sores and to provide training for Georgian doctors.

CIL's Mr. Dzneladze later presented a proposal and budget to the Minister of Health in order to address the life-threatening pressure sores of a list of Georgian wheelchair users. CIL had completed negotiations with an Armenian specialist in pressure sore surgery, Dr. Oganessian, to visit Georgia, conduct at least 10 surgeries and to have Georgian doctors attend the surgeries and learn surgical techniques from him. CIL identified two Georgian doctors willing to be trained as well. Unfortunately, the Minister of Health angrily responded that Georgia did not have anyone with pressure sores and that there was sufficient prevention, medical care and rehabilitation already available in Georgia. In response, CIL collected photos and statements of about 20 wheelchair users with severe pressure sores and demonstrated the current lack of pressure sore education, prevention and medical care in Georgia, both among medical professionals as well as wheelchair users themselves and their family members.

While there is strong interest by Georgian wheelchair users in developing a public education campaign, no one is stepping forward to volunteer to be public educators on this topic and to be responsible for conducting several public education meetings. WID asked CIL to continue working on this problem of identifying appropriate individuals who were willing to take on responsibility for implementing several public education seminars.

b. How these problems were resolved

Resolution of WID Management Problems and Challenges

WWI and SFSU Financial Management Issues

The WID project director remained optimistic that WWI would be able to resolve its operational and reporting complications with the SFSU administration. However, these problems continued and intensified during the second year and the third year of the project, which created a lot of additional frustration and work for WID. Therefore, during the project extension, WID continued to involve WWI as a technical consultant with no management or supervision responsibilities in order to maintain the critical technical expert involvement of WWI's international consultant, Mr. Afonin.

WWI Program Management Issues

In early 2010, WID had to assume a greater role in the implementation of the postural support seating service project component than was previously assumed. WID's project director, Mr. Curtis, had to step in and help manage the postural support seating equipment and services project component, and with assistance from Mr. Noon, Mr. Curtis had to quickly deconstruct and learn this field of work in order to have the capacity to coordinate the implementation of this activity with all Georgian partners. By April 2011, the beginning of the 3rd project year, the NDC (then CCNRR) postural support seating equipment and services component activity was satisfactorily on schedule and producing excellent results.

It was necessary for WID to assume several of WWI's dropped project responsibilities in the second and third year of the project. For the implementation of the project components of Wheelchair Production, Postural Support Seating Services and Regional Wheelchair Sales and Repair Shops, during the first three project years, it became necessary for WID to provide a much higher level of ongoing management and supervision involvement for these three project components than was originally planned and budgeted. Therefore, during the 2-year project extension, WID continued to involve WWI only as a technical consultant, with minimal management or supervision responsibilities, in order to maintain the critical technical expert involvement of WWI's international consultant, Mr. Afonin.

Resolution of WID Program Implementation Problems and Challenges

USAID Reduction of WID's Original 3-Year Project Budget in 2009

WID and its American and Georgian partners made a strong and credible attempt to fulfill all of their project management and implementation responsibilities over the first three years of the project and during the two years of supplemental project funding. All of the project partners were extremely creative and very cost conscious when implementing project programs and activities. All of the project partners' administrative staff worked long days, and sometimes weekends and holidays, in order to professionally complete required project activities to the best of their abilities.

Submission of Quarterly Program and Financial Reports by Deadlines

WID had several conversations with WWI and CIL to resolve their delays in submitting reports on time. WWI reviewed all of their previously submitted quarterly reports and modified their narrative section to more accurately reflect the detail of the work that they have accomplished.

CIL met with their 2 regional partners and after discussions decided to revise their collaborative working relationship going forward. Up until October 2010, CIL had difficulties with the

regional partners', GDC and DEA, inability to fulfill their project activities according to the project work plan. CIL decided to experiment with a new management strategy of taking direct responsibility for the implementation of the regional project activities, with participation and assistance from the regional DPOs, in order to ensure that all of the work plan activities are implemented and were as productive as possible. This strategy worked, and the regional DPOs' ability to manage and implement their activities significantly improved from project year 3 onward. CIL assumed responsibility for the collection and reporting of all required project statistics in order to ensure consistency and accuracy of the statistics that WID reported. The results of this decision could be seen in the improvement in quarterly reports from CIL.

Partners' Problems with World Learning/USAID Statistical and Financial Forms

In February 2012, the WID site visit to Georgia had as its primary objectives to review the accounting and recordkeeping of CIL and also, with CIL participation, the review and modification of all 11 quarterly report's indicators form. After reviewing and modifying as necessary the indicator forms, a total of 11 Quarterly indicator forms were resubmitted to WL and accepted.

This review of CIL accounting procedures and documentation increased WID's level of confidence in the accuracy and transparency of CIL's accounting procedures and also WID's understanding of the administrative structure supporting CIL as WID prepared to take over direct management and supervision of CIL's sub award for the wheelchair production and provision component in the project extension instead of WWI/SFSU continuing as an intermediary.

Minimal And Unchanging Government Budget For Addressing Disability Issues

In March 2013, WID continued communicating with CIL and NDC regarding their advocacy activities towards the government adopting an increased national budget for disability services and for including new services and products (electric wheelchairs, basic wheelchair assessment, postural support seating services) within the Ministry of Health voucher program. The Deputy Minister of Health was appointed by the previous government and political party and is directly responsible for managing the prices and items covered by the national voucher system. CIL's Mr. Dzneladze met several times with the Deputy Minister of Health and strongly advocated that they increase the amount of money paid by the government under the voucher program for manual wheelchairs.

Lack of Enforcement of the Government Law on Architectural Accessibility

In March 2012, the CIL advocacy team and representatives of other CIL member organizations met with the Minister of Regional Development and Infrastructure in order to discuss the need for using standards of universal design during ongoing and future construction works initiated and funded by the Ministry. CIL also discussed mechanisms and ways of future cooperation between CIL and the Ministry in order to ensure newly built infrastructure is accessible. The Ministry agreed to organize a large meeting with representatives of 63 municipalities to raise their awareness about persons with physical disabilities and the need to make certain that all new buildings will have accessible infrastructure. The Ministry also agreed to help organize a meeting with donor organizations that might be interested in funding/co-funding accessible adaptation work.

CIL closely cooperated with the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia to review the existing construction standards and develop an updated and comprehensive document of internationally agreed standards, submitted by the Ministry of Economy to the Ministry of Justice for approval.

In early 2014, CIL met with local wheelchair users, their parents and family members in Tbilisi to inform them about the new government resolution, *Resolution on Ensuring Accessibility of Architectural and Infrastructural Facilities for Persons with Disabilities*, which will ensure existing and future building infrastructure accessibility and was issued in December 2013. CIL wanted to make sure that the local disabled community was involved with informing government decision-makers about the accessibility requirements of the new resolution as well as about enforcing its implementation.

National Voucher System Wheelchair Price is Too Low

In 2011, in order to increase wheelchair sales by capturing the largest possible market share of these voucher holders, CIL developed a public marketing plan and a system of telephone sales calls to the eligible list of holders of vouchers in order to educate them about the benefits of selecting the CIL RoughRider™ wheelchair for their voucher, which included follow-up support service. No other Georgian wheelchair importer and reseller were offering the same wheelchair quality guarantees or follow-up support services as CIL.

CIL also learned that they must build in the cost for conducting a face-to-face wheelchair assessment, additional CIL voucher administration paperwork and any additional transportation cost for wheelchair deliver into their next Government wheelchair purchase tender bid. This means CIL must continue advocating to the government for a higher wheelchair voucher price.

Mr. Dzneladze met many times in 2013 with the Deputy Minister of Health and strongly requested that they increase the amount of money paid by the government under the voucher program for manual wheelchairs. In a meeting of the National Disability Council in June 2013, CIL's Mr. Dzneladze publicly discussed his problems with the current government pricing for wheelchairs under the voucher system. In response, Prime Minister Ivanishvili directed the Ministry of Health officials to research and evaluate the pricing of wheelchairs and other disability services under the Ministry of Health voucher program.

CIL collaborated with the Ministry of Health in their research and evaluation efforts to establish a new government voucher price for wheelchairs. In August 2013, CIL succeeded in their negotiation efforts with the Ministry of Labor, Healthcare and Social Affairs to change the Georgian government policy on wheelchair provision tenders in order to bring the government tender qualifications into compliance with modern international standards and World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines on wheelchair provision.

On August 22, 2013, as a result of 6 months of meetings and discussions by CIL with the Ministry of Labor, Health and Social Affairs, the Government of Georgia (GoG) issued a new resolution on wheelchair provision on August 22, 2013, according to which starting from September 1, 2013, there will be a new separate state program for purchasing wheelchairs (both manual and electric) called "Supporting local wheelchair production and employment of PWD."

This GoG amendment sets out tender eligibility criteria according to which only those local wheelchair providers are eligible to provide wheelchairs within the state program, who produce wheelchairs locally; employ PWD in their production; and have all the technical and human capacity, technology and methodology to follow the WHO guidelines on wheelchair provision, which requires basic assessment and fitting, training, technical service and postural support seating service, when needed.

The Completion of the First CIL Wheelchair Production Shop

In the beginning of 2010, WWI technical consultant, Mr. Afonin, worked very hard with CIL to quickly finish the setup of the wheelchair production shop. By June 2010, all necessary renovations to the workshop and the production machines and tools were purchased and installed and three wheelchairs were completed and given to individuals for field-testing and for reporting on quality and effectiveness in the Georgian environment. The reports from the disabled Georgians testing the wheelchair prototypes were very positive.

WID also had to assume a greater role in the implementation of the wheelchair production shop work plan due to the amount of management time, which is required in Georgia in order to coordinate such a complex group of partners and activities.

WWI relied on its Russian consultant, Mr. Afonin, who was spending six months out of the year in Georgia, helping to set up the production shop and train the CIL production team. This time intensive use of Mr. Afonin on the ground in Georgia was how the project partners had originally conceived that WWI would assist CIL to set up the production shop and it worked amazingly well and beyond our expectations. The production shop successfully began producing wheelchairs. However, the wheelchair production shop success was only possible due to Mr. Afonin's commitment and personal creativity and because of WID and WWI stepping in numerous times to problem solve implementation obstacles. Special acknowledgement of this important project accomplishment must be given to Mr. Afonin for his immense contribution to the success of this project.

Constructing Pressure Relieving Cushions

In October 2013, Mr. Constantinescu's Company, Diversability Development Organization (DDO), contacted NDC regarding a prototype pressure-relief cushion, which they wanted field-tested in Georgia prior to starting commercial production and sales. The new DDO D-Slim cushion has been tested by an accredited lab in the USA and met all the requirements for U.S. Medicare coding for the E2603 Skin Protection Cushion.

The new DDO Slim pressure-relief cushions are cheaper than the pressure relief cushions supplied by UCP from Indonesia and also cheaper than the \$13 comfort cushion CIL can make in Georgia. That means that CIL and NDC can buy a pressure relief cushion from DDO for less than it cost to make a comfort cushion. The DDO Slim cushions will be made in China and can be shipped to Georgia through CIL's shipping contact in Beijing.

Results from the field trial were very positive with all wheelchair users expressing their satisfaction with the DDO Slim pressure-relief cushion. Visual inspection of trial cushions from DDO and an informal interview with one test of a DDO cushion sample indicated no significant

failures, adequate durability and some minor feedback for the supplier to improve the product. DDO has quoted prices of between \$11.50-\$12.50 and CIL ordered 300 DDO Slim pressure relief cushions.

In March 2014, it was recommended that, although good pressure relieving cushions can be ordered very cheaply from DDO, it is still important for CIL to maintain the capacity to locally produce pressure relief cushions, if there were ever obstacles to importing cushions. To demonstrate local production capacity, a future plan has been laid out by CIL that includes the order of high quality foam from sources in Turkey after the end of the project.

Wheelchair Provision Includes a Pressure Relief Cushion when Needed

CIL's Mr. Dzeladze told the government that the international standard for wheelchair provision required always providing an appropriate cushion with the wheelchairs. Wheelchairs should not be sold without the proper type of cushions, including pressure relief cushions and that payment for comfort or pressure relieving cushions must be included in the government tender price for purchasing wheelchairs. CIL continued its efforts to educate and convince Government authorities to change the voucher price for wheelchairs to include a comfort cushion or a pressure relieving cushion and CIL continued their efforts to reduce the cost of producing a locally made, good quality pressure-relieving cushion.

Need for Wheelchair Screening Workshop with Social Workers

In February 2012, CIL began conducting periodic one-day workshops for social workers working for the Ministry of Labor, Healthcare and Social Affairs as social agents in communities throughout Georgia. This training provided basic disability awareness and information about the quality and mobility differences between various models of wheelchairs including the RoughRider™ wheelchair. CIL is planning to utilize the community networks of the social workers in order to educate their clients who need wheelchairs about the different choices available when using their vouchers. Appropriately trained social workers could help to reduce the amount of time required by CIL staff to answer basic information questions from wheelchair voucher recipients.

In March 2014, CIL and NDC OTs, with input from WID and Jamie Noon, developed a more substantive curriculum and conducted a one-day model training for social workers from West Georgia, on how to identify the needs of wheelchair users and how to screen them for an appropriate wheelchair. CIL worked with the National Social Service Agency to identify capable and willing social workers interested in learning more about how to work with wheelchair users and to help with identifying their measurements and needs for a wheelchair. 18 social workers from 8 cities, Kutaisi, Sachkhere, Mestia, Martvili, Ozurgeti, Zugdidi, Poti and Batumi, attended the training conducted by CIL and NDC wheelchair service providers (Levan Talakhadze, Nino Rukhadze and Ilo Volkashov). By the end of the training, the majority of the social workers felt confident enough to determine which service level was appropriate for potential wheelchair recipients; take basic body measurements for wheelchair screening; and refer them to professional service providers if a higher level of service was needed. CIL will continue conducting training in wheelchair provision screening for social workers and after several trainings will identify those social workers most capable and willing to undergo training in WHO Basic wheelchair service.

Future 5-Day Wheelchair Mobility Skills/Active Rehabilitation Camps

In 2014, CIL began working to raise funds from donor organizations and the private sector in order to continue conducting 5-Day wheelchair skills mobility/active rehabilitation and independent living skills training after the project funding ended. Currently, CIL is communicating with TBC Bank, which is known for funding various social and art projects. Giorgi Dzneladze and Rati Ionatamishvili have already met with the Public Relations office of TBC Bank to inform them about the idea and are now developing an official proposal.

One-Day Wheelchair Mobility Skills Training Events

By March 2011, all of the project partners agreed to experiment with providing several local, one-day wheelchair mobility skills training events. The logistics of a one-day event were much easier to organize and implement for the DPO partners and made it possible to increase the numbers of wheelchair users who received some mobility skills training with new RoughRider™ wheelchairs and some independent living skills training.

Implementation of Postural Support Seating Equipment and Services

By April 2010, WID successfully developed a new partnership and signed a sub award with The Treatment and Educational Center of Child Neurology and Neuro Rehabilitation (CCNNR, renamed Neuro Development Center in 2012) located in Tbilisi, to provide a postural support seating service for disabled adults and children in Georgia. CCNNR is the only children's rehabilitation center in Georgia and provides satellite services in other rehabilitation centers in Georgia. CCNNR also agreed to support a series of training of trainers classes, conducted by Jamie Noon, primarily directed at OTs currently working with CCNNR. A woodworking workshop and a storage facility in the basement of CCNNR was upgraded with some new equipment in order to facilitate their construction and assembly of postural support seating components.

No Public Understanding about Postural Support Seating Equipment and Services

In February 2011, CIL and NDC (then CCNNR) hosted a public presentation of postural support seating production and service availability in Georgia. This first event was very interesting and interactive involving questions from the guests and the audience. Jamie Noon and Zaza Kakushadze of NDC made speeches and presentations. Moris Tsamalashvili, Deputy Minister of Healthcare, and Kent Longsdon, Deputy US Ambassador, greeted the public audience. USAID, World Vision, Everychild and local NGOs and local families attended the event, which was covered by 4 Georgian television channels including Rustavi 2 TV channel.

In April 2013, CIL organized another very successful public information event in order to educate key government authorities and the Georgian public about the newly available adult and children's postural support seating equipment produced by NDC, about the RoughRider™ wheelchairs and the new lightweight and foldable electric RoughRider™ wheelchair produced by the CIL wheelchair production shop. The public presentation was attended by many NGOs, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Education, the Public Defender's Office (Ombudsman), USAID and Mr. Richard Norland, the U.S. Ambassador to Georgia and covered by all of the main Georgian TV stations.

Implementation of Regional Postural Support Seating Services

In April 2010, the WID project director created a budget and work plan for CCNNR (now NDC), which also included a small budget for introducing regional service workshops for adults and children, which were conducted by trained CCNNR OTs. This budget was meant to begin the effort to educate families and professionals in other regions of Georgia about the availability of postural support saving equipment and services. In January 2011, 2 CCNNR OTs were sent to 2 cities in west Georgia, Kutaisi and Batumi, in order to introduce the availability of quality postural support seating equipment and services for children with mobility impairments to professionals and families in these cities. Follow-up seating solution implementation visits to these clients in these two cities were scheduled in the following quarter. The OTs evaluated 29 children and 8 of them were provided full service with a new RoughRider™ wheelchair and postural seating supports and a number of children were put on the list for future service. Subsequent clinics were held in other cities in different regions throughout Georgia.

The Completion of the New CIL Wheelchair Production Shop

In June 2012, CIL leased part of a building located in a commercial neighborhood off of the main highway to the airport and reported that there should be enough space for an office and a wheelchair products showroom in addition to the production lines and storage space.

By August 2012, CIL completely renovated the new building space to house the expanded wheelchair production shop. The building was painted and refurbished and all of the wheelchair production equipment and machinery relocated and set up. Wheelchair accessible workplaces were arranged for all workshop staff and an improved system for ventilation and a used powder coat paint/color recycling system installed.

The renovated building has a total of almost 450 m² of usable space compared to the 150 m² for the first CIL wheelchair production shop. The building was subdivided into a raw materials storage room, a cutting room, a paint room, a general work and assembly area, two accessible bathroom/showers and a separate office. The amount of usable workspace is almost 3 times the size of the first wheelchair production facility. In September 2012, wheelchair production was started up in the new building, and the production of wheelchairs has been ongoing at the new building ever since.

Implementation of a CIL Wheelchair Products Showroom for the Public

After September 2012, and for more than a year later, because there were not any designated project funds for new remodeling or construction, WID and CIL continued discussing different strategies about how to pay for adding on a wheelchair product showroom for the public to the new CIL wheelchair production building since all of the usable space of the renovated building was ultimately completely occupied and used for other production and storage purposes.

In January 2014, CIL finally decided that trying to remodel and construct a public showroom for wheelchairs at the existing wheelchair factory was not cost-effective and more importantly, the location of the wheelchair factory was not convenient for the public to go there since it is located near the airport, which is 25 minutes away from the City Center. Therefore, CIL decided to rent a wheelchair exhibition space within a medical product and supply business, currently located across the street from the main hospital complex, on a major bus line and close to the City

Center. CIL staff is scheduled daily to be at this public showroom, and examples of CIL manual and power wheelchairs, pressure relief cushions and metal ramps are available for the public to easily examine and to buy.

Sustainability of the Wheelchair Production Business

In February 2012, after the most difficult technical issues concerning the day-to-day production of wheelchairs and quality control had been resolved by 2 years of collaboration with CIL, WWI turned to the current and future business and marketing issues confronting CIL. The successful implementation of regional and domestic marketing of their RoughRider™ wheelchair products and support services would help to guarantee CIL's future as a viable wheelchair manufacturing enterprise. WWI staff carried out extensive discussions in CIL's Tbilisi office and business management mentoring, which led to WWI signing a contract with CIL to make them formal partners within the global Whirlwind Franchise Network. This international sales business relationship between WWI and CIL will continue past the project ending.

Implementation of Regional Wheelchair Repair Shops

The CIL wheelchair production specialists Levan Talakhadze and Tamaz Injgia, with the help from WWI consultant Sasha Afonin, conducted a week-long training in wheelchair maintenance and repair in the beginning of December 2011 for Joni Gergedava from Zugdidi and Malkhaz Ioramashvili from Gori, who were trained to be mechanics at wheelchair repair shops set up in their respective cities.

In mid-2012, the Zugdidi wheelchair repair shop was created in the renovated garage building in the backyard of the Association DEA office, and in Gori, the wheelchair repair shop was built into the building owned and operated by the Gori Disabled Club. In September 2012, CIL provided equipment and tools to the wheelchair repair shops in Gori and Zugdidi and purchased wheelchair parts and bearings for the wheelchair mechanics to use while providing repair services to local wheelchair users.

Training in Micro-Business Management for Regional Wheelchair Repair Mechanics

CIL is also working with International Organization of Migration (IOM) Georgian office to provide training in micro-business management to Gori and Zugdidi wheelchair repair staff. IOM is currently implementing a training program for mine victims teaching them basic business management and financial accounting skills and has already agreed to include Joni Gergedava (who is a mine victim) from Zugdidi and Malkhaz Ioramashvili and Ito Karkishvili from Gori in their next training in micro-business management.

Underperformance of the Community Accessibility Barrier Removal Mini-Projects

In October 2012, WID and CIL brought all of the regional community advocacy team members together for a group advocacy training, along with new volunteers, in order to strengthen their understanding and methodologies for implementing the 1-day mobility skills training events and for implementing more community barrier removal projects. In early 2013, WID communicated to CIL its concerns about the continuing underperformance of the regional community advocacy team and asked them to provide greater encouragement and support to the community advocacy teams for increasing the number of their community barrier removal activities. WID continued to

monitor their community barrier removal activities and met with all 3 community advocacy teams in September 2013 in order to review their current list of barrier removal projects; to provide any needed technical assistance; and to encourage a final push to increase the number of completed barrier removal projects in their communities.

Need for Public Education about Pressure Sores and the Total Lack of Medical Services to Treat Pressure Sores in Georgia

CIL developed a budget and submitted it to the Healthcare Minister with a request to organize the transportation of a professional surgeon from Armenia in order to conduct several surgeries on Georgian wheelchair users who have pressure sores and are currently in life-threatening condition and to train Georgian doctors. After approval of the international expert training request by the Ministry of Health, CIL conducted negotiations with an Armenian specialist in pressure sore surgery to visit Georgia, conduct at least 10 surgeries and to have Georgian doctors attend the surgeries and learn successful medical techniques from him. The Armenian surgeon, Mr. Artak Oganessian, visited Tbilisi in December 2013, during which he also met with the Georgian doctors and evaluated the conditions of several patients awaiting surgery. He also visited two Georgian hospitals (Ghudushauri and the Patriarchate's clinics) where the pressure sore medical care program was to be implemented (surgery and post-surgery rehabilitation).

At the same time, CIL began working with the Healthcare Ministry to develop a Government program on pressure sore prevention and medical treatment, which is already described in the *2014-2016 State Action Plan on Providing Equal Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities*, which was developed by CIL's Disability Advocacy Project and funded by the USAID Mission to Georgia. The above-listed activities are considered significant progress towards establishing pressure sore prevention and medical care in Georgia.

CIL staff also developed a budget and submitted it to the Ministry of Health for consideration in December. In March 2014, CIL received official agreement from the Ministry to allocate funds for the surgeries and the travel of Dr. Oganessian from Armenia. Currently, the Ministry has agreed to pay for 7 surgeries for those individuals who are in the most critical condition, but CIL is also working with the Ministry to increase funding and to pay for surgeries of other people who are on a waiting list.

VI. Financial Position

a. Total Budget and Expenses (presented by major categories)

	TOTAL BUDGET	TOTAL EXPENSES	FUNDS REMAINING
Personnel	\$453,313	\$465,998	(\$12,685)
Fringe Benefits	\$115,214	\$108,825	\$6,389
Consultants	\$179,933	\$172,138	\$7,795
Travel & Transportation	\$131,128	\$130,435	\$693
Equipment	\$0	\$0	\$0
Other Direct Costs	\$182,987	\$182,301	\$686
Program Activities	\$0	\$0	\$0
Sub-grants	\$1,368,209	\$1,368,209	\$0
Indirect Costs	\$232,216	\$231,667	\$549
TOTAL	\$2,663,000	\$2,659,574	\$3,426

Program income was part of the project. During the project, CIL generated \$658,604 in wheelchair sales income. The project incrementally reduced its subsidy of the wheelchair production shop, so wheelchair sales income was all put back into the project to cover expenses that were no longer covered by the project.

b. Compare Total Budget vs. Expenses (provide explanation if there is a deviation more than 10%). If any of the line items are over spent, please provide an explanation. Be aware that Equipment or Indirect line items may not be overspent.

The personnel line was overspent by \$12,685 (just under 2.8%). The overage of Personnel in May, and the corresponding reduced Fringe Benefits, are the result of the end of Program personnel lay-off and accrued vacation payout. As the vacation has been accrued over the years through the Fringe Benefits line item, the payout of that accrued vacation transfers those funds into the Salary/Personnel line (and balances by crediting the Fringe Benefits). \$7,896.25 is due to the vacation benefits charged in May (the same amount was deducted from fringe benefits to zero-out). The rest is the increase in Jennifer Geagan’s FTE from 60% to 100% in the month of May. WID had no purchases in the Equipment line, and Indirect was slightly underspent (\$549).

c. List each calendar year during which the project was implemented and the amount (in USD) of interest, if any, earned during that year.

- 2009: \$0
- 2010: \$0
- 2011: \$0
- 2012: \$0
- 2013: \$0
- 2014: \$0

VII. Documentation of Shared Learning

a. Please see the Independent Final Evaluation Report

VIII. Recommendations to World Learning for improvements of the grant management process

Please see closeout document #5 End-of-Project Grantee Feedback Form.